

The Offences related to Cyber Crime in India: A Critical Study with respect to Present Day Challenges

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Abstract

Crime is a very old concept. However the nature of crime has been changed by the change of time. From 20th century with the invention of computer criminals preferred crimes from traditional methods to computer based methods. The first recorded cyber crime took place in the year 1820.² Cyber law means the law relating to control and prevent cyber crimes. The term 'cyber crime' has not been defined anywhere however cyber law generally deals with all aspect of electronic communication. In digital era, new generation crime through internet is known cyber crime. Due to its transnational nature, every country is obliged to make a special law dealing with cyber crime and our country has also enacted the Information Technology Act, 2000, in this regard.

Key Words: Crime, Cyber Crime, Internet, Electronic communication, Information Technology.

I. Introduction:

Cyber crime is mainly a crime which relates to the computer, other digital devices and the networks and is committed against individuals or group of individuals with a criminal motive to intentionally harm the reputation of the victim through internet.³ At present internet became indispensable and increasing day by day and some people utilizing this opportunity who have ill intention to misuse the social media sites or the other internet sites for fulfilling their purposes which is not legal. Nowadays it is a serious challenge in law to combat various types of cyber crimes because criminals are also inventing new processes of committing crime day by day. Sometimes government or business organizations may get attacked by cyber crimes. The main intention of cyber criminals is to attack information system and programmes as well as data of computer. Cyber crime can be classified into three groups.⁴ There are many types of cyber crimes and some of them are hacking,

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²https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/bitstream/10603/203654/8/08_chapter%203.pdf, assessed on 26.03.2020 at 6.30 p.m.

³ <http://www.allbachelor.com/computer/class10/shortnotes/4.cyberlaw.html>, last accessed on 24/08/2019.

⁴ <https://www.crossdomainsolutions.com/cyber-crime/>, last accessed on 24/8/2019.

Crime against property: Like real life theft, robbery etc. can be happened in cyber world too. For example in case of cyber world the criminals can steal bank details of a person and drain off money. By misusing credit cards they can purchase things online, they use malicious software to gain access to different websites of the organizations or disorder the system of the organizations. Hardware and software both can be damaged by the malicious software. It is likely to vandals damage property of the world outside the online world i.e. offline world.

theft, cyber stalking, malicious software, identity theft, child soliciting, virus dissemination, computer vandalism, cyber terrorism⁵.

II. Rationale and Scope of the Study:

The inquisitiveness with respect to know about the various types of offences committed through cyber space, the remedies provided by the law to the victim propelled the author to study in this direction. The scope is to know about the usefulness of the Information Technology Act, 2000 with respect to cyber crime.

III. Literature Review and Research Methodology:

In any research, literature review plays an important role. It is not only important but also essential when the author writes about any research report. It is a required homework that ought to have been done carefully. It is a fact finding task and initial step of any research. It depicts the pictures about what research has been done in the past of the topic chosen by the researcher. A good number of studies relevant for the present study have been studied. This study will be partly empirical and partly doctrinal. In Doctrinal part, two types of reference will be used i.e. primary sources and secondary sources. Primary sources consist of statute and legislations and secondary sources are books, journals, articles. In Empirical part, the primary data will be obtained by field survey from common people to assess the knowledge of the common people with respect to the study. The sample of 40 persons were taken up and interviewed. For empirical study the researcher proposes to adopt field survey method for data collection from selected areas by means of interview through questionnaires. Basically the structured/close ended questionnaires were asked. Questionnaire method is helpful to collect data from large, diverse and widely scattered people. Accordingly 20 common people were interviewed, who were resident of Chinsurah sub-division under Hooghly District of West Bengal and 20 common people were interviewed, who were resident of Barrackpore sub-division under North 24 Parganas District of West Bengal. The information has been collected on stratified random sampling method. The data obtained through the field survey is processed and presented in appropriate tables, columns, pie diagrams for deriving conclusions. Simple statistical tools like percentages, is used for deriving inferences and conclusions.

Crime against individuals: Cyber stalking, distributing, trafficking, etc. are the types of cyber crime against the individuals. Now a days these cyber crime are being considered very serious by the law enforcement agencies. And to check these type of crimes is now a global concern.

Crime against the Government: Crime against a government may be called cyber terrorism. In this case, criminals may hack the websites of the Governments, websites of the military or circulate propaganda. The committers can be terrorist outfits or unfriendly Govt. or other nations.

⁵ Poulami Ghosh submitted her dissertation topic on Cyber Crime to the Department of Law, the University of Burdwan in the year 2019.

IV. Research Questions:

The basic questions which the present study has raised for considerations are:

1. What is the present rate of cyber crime in India?
2. Is the existing law adequate to handle the issue?
3. What changes are needed in the Act to better handle the issue?

V. Hypothesis:

The author has framed the following Hypothesis:

“In Indian context, the Information Technology Act, 2000 has strongly handled the issue of cyber crime and is adequate to protect the interest of common citizen from cyber crime and is adequate to address the challenges arising out from cyber revolution.”

VI. History of Cyber Crime and Cyber Crime law:

Cyber crime is mainly related to computer.⁶ The first mechanical computer was invented by Charles Babbage in 1822 and fully transistorized computer design was introduced in 1958. The invention of internet was the most important event of 20th century. By the term “cyber crime” we mainly understand hacking. With the propagation of email during late 80’s, the first major wave of cybercrime came. It allowed different malware to be delivered to inbox of the people. The second wave of cyber crime came in 90’s with the advancement of web browsers. At that time viruses could be delivered through internet networks during visit of questionable websites.⁷ In the era of social media, the rate of cyber crime started to increase rapidly though exactly the origin of cyber crime cannot be mentioned properly.⁸ In India, internet was available through ERNET at first and Videsh Sanchar Nigam Limited made it accessible for commercial use in August 1995. The first recorded crime in India happened in 1998 at Bhaba atomic research centre by the teenagers. In India, the main cause for passing of the Information Technology Act, 2000 was to protect the interest of the users of the internet, however, this Act is basically based on the United Nations Commission on International Trade Law. The Act promotes e-commerce; Improves business by issuing digital signature by the authorities authorized by this Act; filling online forms for the purposes like promotion of e-governances.⁹ Though there are penal provisions in the Indian Penal

⁶Rajlakshmi Pushkaraj Wagh, “Legal Challenges in Control of Cyber Crime: A Critical Study”, a thesis submitted at Shri Jagdish Prasad Jhabarmal Tibrewala University.

Also available at <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/138517>

⁷ Supra note 5.

⁸ <https://www.le-vpn.com/history-cyber-crime-origin-evolution/>, last accessed on 24/8/2019.

⁹ Supra note 5.

Some loopholes of the I.T. Act 2008 are copyright infringement was not included there; domain names lack protection; there were no provisions of trusts, power of attorney and wills under that Act; the Act was silent

Code and the Information Technology Act but there were no sign of decrease in the rate of crime. The government also passed some other rules to betterment of the situation.¹⁰

VII. Nature of Cyber Crime:

In cyber crime a computer and a network is used to commit crimes like hacking, cyber terrorism, copyright violation, accessing business secrets or personal information unlawfully, disseminating child pornography etc. There are various theories¹¹ of cyber crime. The concept of cyber crime is not radically different from the concept of conventional crime.¹² Offences committed on cyber space

about taxation; Electronic documents were lack of stamp duty; there were no proper law for the governance of credit card frauds; most importantly all offences were not covered by this Act.

¹⁰ These are

1. “The Information Technology (Certifying Authorities) Rules, 2000 was passed for regulation of rules and guidelines for certifying authorities.
2. The Cyber Regulations Appellate Tribunal (Procedure) Rules, 2000 by the central government by exercising powers under section 87 of the ITAA 2008.
3. The Information Technology (Certifying Authority) Regulations, 2001.
4. The Cyber Regulations Appellate Tribunal (Procedure for Investigation of Misbehaviour or Incapacity of Presiding officer) Rules, 2003.
5. The Information Technology (Other Powers of Civil Court vested in Cyber Appellate Tribunal) Rules, 2003.
6. The Information Technology (Other Standards) Rules, 2003
7. The Information Technology (Qualification and Experience of Adjudicating Officers and Manner of Holding enquiry) Rules, 2003.
8. The Cyber Regulations Appellate Tribunal (Salary, Allowances and other Terms and Conditions of Service of Presiding Officer) Rules, 2003
9. The Information Technology (Use of Electronic Records and Digital Signatures) Rules, 2004.”
10. The Cyber Appellate Tribunal (Procedure for Investigation of Misbehaviour or Incapacity of Chairperson and Members) Rules, 2009.”

¹¹Rajlakshmi Pushkaraj Wagh, “Legal Challenges in Control of Cyber Crime: A Critical Study”, a thesis submitted at Shri Jagdish Prasad Jhabarmal Tibrewala University.

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Choice Theory: According to this theory people commit crime of their choice that means they select to commit the crime.

Trait theory: This theory is based on biological and psychological conditions of criminal. According to this theory people commit crime due to their biological and psychological conditions and they do not have any morality. They are always confused between right and wrong and what is law of the society. According to this theory as different people have different genetic order they have different mentality too.

Social Process Theory: According to this theory the mentality of a person may based on the family, educational background. According to this theory the above mentioned factors make the crime to be committed.

Social Structure Theory: According to this theory, society plays very important role in committing crime. Society influences the commission of crime. Lack of education is also another factor for commission of crime.

Conflict Theory: This theory takes the social structure into consideration. A society is formed based on persons, their livelihood etc. However the combination of all these theory influence or give explanation how crimes committed.

Theory of Technology: This theory helps to understand how computer and technologies influence cyber crime.

¹² Cyber crime-Law & policy perspectives, Dr. Mrs. K. Sita Manikyam (2009) Hind Law House, Pune.

are known as cyber crime.¹³The most salient features of these types of crime are that they are easy to commit, difficult to detect and even harder to prove because evidence against the crime is easy to erase¹⁴. By nature they may be classified as crime affecting Individual; crime affecting economy; crime affecting national security.¹⁵

VIII. International aspect of Cyber Crime:

Cybercrime is the most burning topic in today's world. The USA¹⁶ created new laws which regulate the activities on internet and they are National Infrastructure Protection Act, 1996; the Cyberspace Electronic Security Act, 2001 and the Patriot Act, 2001. In England, the Data Protection Act, 1984 and the Computer Misuse Act, 1990 are the two main statutes dealing with cyber crime. The Canadian Parliament in the year 2001 passed the Criminal Law Amendment Act. The Kenyan Parliament passed the Kenya Communication (Amendment) Act. In Norway, a Bill on a new criminal law (2008 to 2009) has introduced. In International level, the current treaty is Budapest Treaty/ Convention on Cybercrime which was laid down in France and signed in 2001 and came into force in 2004. The main objective of this treaty was to have a common policy of nations regarding crime to give protection to the society at large and this will also aid in global cooperation among nations to fight against cyber war. A need is felt by the United Nations to protect the rights of human being in cyber space. Now there is no internationally accepted cyber crime treaty. Efforts are made by UN to accept extra complete and truly worldwide international cyber crime agreement but it was not accepted. India does not have signed convention on cybercrime which may cause a negative effect on Information technology Act, 2000.

IX. Indian Penal Code and Cyber Crime:

After the passing of the Information Technology Act, 2000, certain amendments have been incorporated in the Indian Penal Code to bring the offences under the preview of IPC. The Information Technology Act, 2000 contains wide range of offences such as tampering with computer sources, sending offensive messages, violation of privacy; publishing obscene material, which are already recognized as an offence in Indian Penal Code, for example, sending threatening messages by email (Section 503 IPC); sending defamatory messages by email (Section 499 IPC); forgery of electronic records (Section 463 IPC); bogus websites, cyber frauds (Section 420 IPC);

¹³ Cybercrime: Talat Fatima,(2011) Eastern Book Company Lucknow.

¹⁴ Supra note 2.

¹⁵ Laws on Cyber Crime: P .K. Singh, (2007) Book Enclave, Jaipur.

¹⁶https://docs.google.com/viewerng/viewer?url=https://www.assignmentpoint.com/wp-content/uploads/2015/02/An-International-Perspective-on-Cyber-Crime.doc&hl=en_US

Email spoofing (Section 463 IPC); Web-jacking (Section 383 IPC); E-Mail Abuse (Section 500 IPC); Pornographic (Section 292 IPC).

X. The Information Technology Act, 2000:

The Information Technology Act, 2000 mostly deals with the e-business and the regulation of ecommerce, regulation of digital signature still it recognized certain cyber crime¹⁷. However, the I.T. Act does not exclusively deal with cyber crime and other criminal laws also deal with the cyber crime.¹⁸The I.T Act is not fully deals with the all cyber crime but it needs the support of the conventional criminal law. Many cybercrimes for which no express provisions existed in the IT Act, 2000 now included by the IT (Amendment) Act, 2008. The IT Act has not covered all the cyber crimes and therefore Indian Penal code is applicable in that case. Due to the universal nature of the IPC, it covers almost all the crime.¹⁹

XI. Indian Judiciary:²⁰

In Lakshmi Prathapan vs State of Kerala²¹, the Court came to the conclusion that offences alleged are not clear to come under the purview of Section 66E of the Information Technology Act and hence quashed the criminal proceedings. In State vs. Mohd. Afzal and Ors.²², the Court accepted the computer printouts as evidence as it satisfied the requirements to be an admissible evidence under the I. T. Act as they were certified. However on 24th March 2015 the Apex Court of India squashed section 66A of the I.T. Act, 2000 as unconstitutional. The case laws upon which the verdict was based are Dilipkumar Tulsidas v. UOI²³; Rajeev Chandrasekhar v. Union of India²⁴; Shreya Singhal v. Union of India²⁵. In Sekar v. The Principle General Manager (Telecom) (BSNL)²⁶, one I.T. professional convicted for hacking the government website under section 420 of IPC and section 66 of the Information Technology Act.

¹⁷ Supra note 2.

¹⁸ Rodney D, 'Guide to cyber Laws', Ryder (2003), Wadhwa Publication, Nagpur.

¹⁹https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/bitstream/10603/203654/8/08_chapter%203.pdf, assessed on 26.03.2020 at 6.30 p.m.

²⁰ Supra note 5.

²¹ MANU/ KE/2380/214

²² MANU/DE/1026/2003

²³ WP(C) No 97 of 2013

²⁴ W.P(C) No 23, 2013

²⁵ (2013) 12 SCC 73

²⁶ W.P. (MD) No.10905 of 2005.

XII. Dispute Settlement under I. T. Act:

Cyber Appellate Tribunal has been created as the dispute settlement machinery under the Information Technology Act²⁷. The Act considers a specialized dispute resolution mechanism for disputes relating to the offences under this Act.²⁸ This Act provides for the Quasi Judicial Bodies like adjudicating officers under section 46 who deals with the dispute arising out of chapter IX of this Act. However if anyone is not satisfied with the decision of the Adjudicating officer, the first appeal lies on the Cyber Appellate Tribunal and the second appeal lies on the High Court having jurisdiction.

XIII. Present day Challenges:

Now a days, it has become a challenge to protect the decency, morality and privacy because it has become very easy to publish obscene material. Therefore to make balance between cyber crime and the right of privacy is very important. Cyber terrorism is another big issue for today's world and is a matter of concern. Another challenge is e-contract. In e-contract, computer is used as the tool of formation of contract so it is hard to know whether valid consent has been given or not. Next problem comes with cancellation of offer or revocation as all the process is so fast that sometimes it becomes impossible to revoke the offer before acceptance. It is very difficult to understand whether the consent is free from all type of undue influences or not. Securing intellectual property rights has also become a great challenge in cyber space. Giving conviction of cyber crime accused becomes a great problem because if anyone does any offence beyond the jurisdiction of India, Indian law cannot convict the offender.

²⁷ <https://cis-india.org/internet-governance/blog/review-of-functioning-of-cyber-appellate-tribunal-and-adjudicatory-officers-under-it-act> ,last accessed on 25/8/2019

²⁸ Vakul Sharma, *Information Technology Law and Practice 129*, (Universal Law Publishing, fourth edition, 2015)

XIV. Data Analysis through Tables, columns, pie diagrams²⁹:

Table 1: Opinion given by common people at Chinsurah Sub-division, Hooghly District

Question Number	Questions put to the Respondents (Total No. of Respondents: 20)	Answers in %	
		YES	NO
1.	Do you ever heard about cyber crime?	90	10
2.	Can you name any one of them?	20	80
3.	Do you think that evidence against the cyber crime is easy to erase?	50	50
4.	Do you ever heard about Information Technology Act, 2000?	30	70
5.	Do you think that the existing law adequate to handle cyber crime?	20	80
6.	Do you think that changes are needed in the Act to better handle cyber crime?	90	10
7.	Do you think that the Act is adequate to address the challenges arising out from cyber revolution?	20	80
No. Of Male Respondent: 10		No. Of Female Respondent: 10	
Age wise -- Male	From 21-30 years: 05	Age wise-- Female	From 21-30 years: 04
	From 31-40 years: 01		From 31-40 years: 02
	From 41-50 years: 02		From 41-50 years: 03
	From 50 and above years: 02		From 50 and above years: 01

²⁹ Field survey by the author.

Table 2: Opinion given by common people at Barrackpore Sub-division, 24PGS (North)

Question Number	Questions put to the Respondents (Total No. of Respondents: 20)	Answers in %	
		YES	NO
1.	Do you ever heard about cyber crime?	85	15
2.	Can you name any one of them?	40	60
3.	Do you think that evidence against the cyber crime is easy to erase?	60	40
4.	Do you ever heard about Information Technology Act, 2000?	40	60
5.	Do you think that the existing law adequate to handle cyber crime?	45	55
6.	Do you think that changes are needed in the Act to better handle cyber crime?	70	30
7.	Do you think that the Act is adequate to address the challenges arising out from cyber revolution?	45	55
No. Of Male Respondent: 11		No. Of Female Respondent: 09	
Age wi se- - M ale	From 21-30 years: 02	Age wis e-- Fe mal e	From 21-30 years: 03
	From 31-40 years: 03		From 31-40 years: 01
	From 41-50 years: 04		From 41-50 years: 04
	From 50 and above years: 02		From 50 and above years: 01

Column No. 1

Column No. 2

Pie diagram No. 1

Pie diagram No. 2

XV. Conclusion and Suggestions:

With the development of society, the nature of crime also changes. Credit card fraud, stealing of intellectual properties, bank account hack, publishing obscene material, child pornography etc. has become very common today. In comparison to growing rate of cyber crime, the control mechanism is still very poor. If the control mechanism cannot be made strong, the next generation will suffer a lot. There is no penal liability under the Act of the Network Service Provider. Huge power has been given to the police. Some legal issues like online rights of consumers, privacy concerns, domain name disputes etc. have not been addressed. It is suggested that the I. T. Act should rectify the shortcomings to better handle the issue of cyber crime. International legal framework ought to be so strong that it can handle cyber crimes strongly. To secure intellectual property rights needful provisions should be included to the Information Technology Act. Public awareness is also very necessary to combat the cyber crime.

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The Public Trust Doctrine: Indian Perspective

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Abstract

The doctrine of public trust has its origin in Roman law. It was accepted and applied by the common law courts in England latter on. The doctrine has been beautifully articulated by the U.S. courts in their domestic law and at present has attained a global status. The public trust doctrine primarily rests on the principle that certain resources like air, sea, waters and the forests have such a great importance to the people as a whole that it would be wholly unjustified to make them a subject of private ownership. The said resources being a gift of nature, they should be made freely available to everyone irrespective of the status in life. Therefore, governments hold and possess these creations as trustee of the public. There exists relationship of trustee and beneficiary between the government and the public. Resultantly, the government cannot exploit these natural creations in an unreasonable and arbitrary manner, ignoring public rights. The doctrine enjoins upon the government to protect the resources for the enjoyment of the general public rather than to permit its use for private ownership or commercial purposes. Though, traditionally the doctrine of public trust was applied only for protection of access to the common property for public benefit, now the doctrine is being applied even to prevent over exploitation of environment and to ensure sustainable development. Now this doctrine is being used as a legal and planning tool for the fulfillment of sovereign's role as trustee of environment for future generations. In the light of this, this paper is an attempt to analyze the Indian perspective of this doctrine.

Catch Words: Environment, Public Trust Doctrine, Sustainable Development.

The Public Trust Doctrine is a part of our environmental law which has its root in the English Common Law. It is also in consonance with the age old Indian Philosophy that the Head or the Ruler/ King is the trustee of all natural resources but at the same time, such responsibility to manage the common property can be transferred to the private persons, not the ownership. Thus, the government has a duty to promote and maintain a healthy environment on behalf of the present and future generations. The duty is not optional, it is a mandatory, affirmative duty that government cannot alienate, abdicate or deny. The State Government is the protector, the guardian, the shield of the public trust. This is a unique and specific duty to protect our common heritage so that we can pass it on to the future generation undamaged, unspoiled and ideally improved.

The real basis of the principle of public trust is public interest and common property which are for the common benefit. Moreover, it can be argued that these natural assets like air, water, land, forests

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etc. can best be managed by the State which would use them for public purpose in comparison to private ownership which would use them for their private benefit. We must be alive to the fact that these remaining representative samples of nature have to be guarded by the State as a trustee against any activity which, in a serious way, interferes with ecology and natural environment.

Origin and Growth of Public Trust Doctrine

The public trust doctrine is an old principle which was originally espoused by the Emperor *Justinian* during the Roman Empire.¹ He declared that: “by the law of nature these three things are common to mankind- the air, running water and the sea and consequently the shores of the sea.” The title to these essential resources is held by the State, as sovereign, in trust for the people. English Common Law has been recognized as the basis of this doctrine. From this Common Law, the doctrine spread to the USA where it deeply imbedded itself in the law and culture.

In *M. C. Mehta v. Kamal Nath*,² the Supreme Court has provided an analysis of English and American law that has applied the public trust doctrine, and comes to the conclusion that the English version of the doctrine is somewhat narrower than the American version. It notes that the English doctrine is restricted to ‘traditional uses such as navigation, commerce and fishing’. Indian courts and legislature have expressed their preference for the American version of the doctrine that ‘encompasses the entire spectrum of the environment’ and contemplates Indian values relating to the environment as defined in international and domestic legal instruments.

Justice Arijit pasayat, in *T. N. Godavarman Thirumalpad v. Union of India*,³ observed that by destroying natural environment, man is committing matricide, having in a way killed Mother Earth. His Lordship observed that “Our legal system based on English Common Law includes the public trust doctrine as a part of its jurisprudence. The State is the trustee of all natural resources which are by nature meant for public use and enjoyment. Public at large is the beneficiary of the seashore, running water, air, forests and ecologically fragile land. The State as trustee is under a legal duty to protect the natural resources. These resources meant for public use cannot be converted into private ownership. The aesthetic use and the pristine glory cannot be permitted to be eroded for private, commercial or any other use unless the courts find it necessary in good faith, for public good and in public interest to encroach upon the said resources.”⁴

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¹ Institute of Justinian: 2.1.1.

² (1997) 1 SCC 388.

³ 2003 (6) SCALE 374.

⁴ *Ibid.*

Indian Perspective of Public Trust Doctrine

In India, it has been recognized, since a long time, that the Kings/ Rulers owe certain 'public duties' including the duty to protect the natural resources and to maintain national resources and national system of irrigation which are of common good and use.⁵ The Madras High Court also declared, almost a century ago, that rights and obligations of government in regard to irrigation work in this country (India) have to be ascertained from unrecorded custom and practices.⁶ The Manusmriti,⁷ which is supposed to be of 300 to 400 B.C. as well as Arthashastra,⁸ of Kautilya recognize the King/ Ruler to be the trustee of the natural resources and not the owner of these resources. This was quoted with approval by Justice Chinnappa Reddy in *S. Sachidanand v. State of W.B.*,⁹ however, till date except some stray instances our literature has not been quoted or referred to by our courts to explain and highlight the public trust doctrine.

Indian legal system, derived from English common law, includes the public trust doctrine. This doctrine forms the crux on which article 47 of the constitution is based.¹⁰ In fact, the objectives enshrined in the Preamble and Directive Principle of State Policy imposes an obligation on the State as well as its citizens to preserve the environment and its use for the maximum benefit of people. The Preamble envisages India to be a 'socialist' State, the main aim of which should be to distribute the common richness and wealth of the country in a way that serves the needs and requirements of the common man.¹¹ This will only suffice the mandate for social and economic transformation as envisaged by the Directive Principle of State Policy.¹² This doctrine finds its contemporary relevance as a 'legal and planning tool for the fulfillment of the sovereign's role as trustee of the environment for future generations'.¹³ Certain statutes reflect the public trust doctrine in certain sections.¹⁴

Various pronouncements of the Supreme Court during the last many years vividly depict that the court has evolved a new environmental jurisprudence. The court has always made it clear that the problem of environmental degradation is a social problem and considering its impact on the society,

⁵ *Madras Railway Co. v. Zamindar of Carvetnagar*, (1874) L.R.I.A. 364.

⁶ *The Secretary of State for India in Council v. Muthuveerama Reddy*, 1910 I.L.R. 34 Mad. 82.

⁷ Manusmriti, VII: 14.

⁸ Kautilya's Arthashastra: 47 (4th ed 1951) P. 36. Translated by Dr. R. Shamasastri 'the earth does not belong to man; man belongs to the earth...' '... for some special purpose gave you (man) dominion over this land and ...' at pp. 1113 and 1114.

⁹ AIR 1987 SC 1109.

¹⁰ *Municipal Council, Ratlam v. Vardhichand*, AIR 1980 SC 1622.

¹¹ *Haryana State Electricity Board v. Suresh*, (1992) 2 SCC 601.

¹² *Samantha v. State of Andhra Pradesh*, (1997) 8 SCC 191.

¹³ S. Shantha Kumar, *Environmental Law: An Introduction* 122 (Bharathiyar University, Tamilnadu, 2001).

¹⁴ The Forest (Conservation) Act, 1980, Section 2.

law courts have to deal with the situation according to justice and fairness. Thus, the courts are duty bound to harmonize between ‘danger to the environment’ and ‘sustainable development’. Justice Krishna Iyer declared that “Judges (and lawyers) are trustees of the human estate, the world’s great heritage; and the robes have a responsibility obligating the use of writ power to regulate modern industry and technology.”¹⁵ Therefore, the State exercising its power to contain and control the environment, regulates the working of the industry and technology. Such regulation includes issuing directions containing developmental activities.

The Supreme Court pointed out in 1980 that it must not be forgotten that article 47 makes it a paramount principle of governance that steps are taken for the improvement of public health as amongst primary duties and human rights have to be respected irrespective of budgetary provisions.¹⁶ This primary duty under article 47 is based on the public trust doctrine. And it was recognized by the court to be the true basis to trigger off the jurisdiction vested for their benefit and as social justice which is due to the people.

As humans are the recent addition to the livestock, their existence and continuity depends on the presence of healthy, pollution free natural environment. Therefore, environmental concerns are as important as human rights. While environmental aspects concerned human rights, human rights are essential for full development of mankind. Thus, the development of mankind depends on the preservation and protection of the commons natural resources.

Judicial Approach towards Public Trust Doctrine

In India, the decision of the Supreme Court in *M. C. Mehta v. Kamal Nath*,¹⁷ is an excellent exposition of the doctrine of public trust. In this case, a lease deed was granted to a Motel for a period of 99 years. Subsequently, Span Motel took over this leased land and it constructed a club. The land that had been leased was land located at the bank of the river Beas. Meanwhile, this Motel encroached upon a substantial area of land that included reserved forest land and it sought to have such encroachment regularized by applying to the Government of India, Ministry of Environment and Forest for another lease of additional land. Permission was refused for a period of four years and it was only in 1993 that this permission was granted. It is important to note that at the time this permission was finally granted and a new lease given, it was Mr. Kamal Nath who was the Minister for Environment and Forests. Mr. Kamal Nath had a substantial stake in the Motel and the Club. Later, there were floods in that area and a substantial portion of the Club was washed away.

¹⁵ The Hindu, ‘Open Page’, Aug. 17, 1999.

¹⁶ *Supra* note 10.

¹⁷ *Supra* note 2.

Following this, the Club authorities decided to divert the course of the river Beas to prevent such an occurrence. Alarmed by this blatant disregard for the environment, a public spirited individual filed a writ petition to prevent this diversion and the attempted reclamation of land from the river to serve the interest of the Club. The Apex Court came down heavily upon the respondents and held that the actions of the Himachal Pradesh State Government were in clear violation of the doctrine of public trust.

In this case, the Supreme Court applied the doctrine of public trust for protection of the environment. Justice Kuldeep Singh has exhaustively gathered information on the public trust doctrine from various juristic writings and decisions of the American courts. Tracing the origin of the public trust doctrine the Court observed that “the ancient roman empire developed a legal theory known as the doctrine of public trust. It was founded on the ideas that certain common properties such as rivers, seashores, forests and the air were held by government in trusteeship for the free and unimpeded use of the general public. Our contemporary concerns about the environment were a very close conceptual relationship to this legal doctrine. Under the Roman law these resources were either owned by no one (*res nullious*) or by everyone in common (*res communious*). Under the English law, however, the sovereign could own these resources but the ownership was limited in nature, the crown could not grant these properties to private owners if the effect was to interfere with the public interests in navigation or fishing. Resources that were suitable for these uses were deemed to be held in trust by the crown for the benefit of the public.”

The court further observed that “our legal system based on English common law includes the public trust doctrine as part of its jurisprudence. The State is the trustee of all natural resources, which are by nature meant for public use and enjoyment. Public at large is the beneficiary of the seashore, running waters, airs, forests and ecologically fragile lands. The State as a trustee is under a legal duty to protect the natural resources. These resources meant for public use cannot be converted into private ownership.”¹⁸ Consequently, in an attempt to enhance the effective use of the principle, again Justice Saghir Ahmad reiterated that “public trust doctrine is a part of the law of the land.”¹⁹ It is to be noted that in this case, the court did not mention the Directive Principle of State Policy and the Fundamental Duties. It is submitted that Article 48-A²⁰ and 51-A (g)²¹ can be read to be a basis

¹⁸ *Ibid.*

¹⁹ *Ibid.*

²⁰ The Constitution of India, Art. 48-A: “The State shall endeavor to protect and improve the environment and to safeguard the forests and wild life of the country.”

²¹ *Id.*, Art. 51- A (g): “It shall be the duty of every citizen of India ... (g) to protect and improve the natural environment including forests, lakes and wildlife and to have compassion for living creatures.”

for this doctrine. This is especially so in the light of decisions of the Apex Court that held that “the directive principles cannot be violated while making a policy or framing a law.”²² Therefore, this doctrine appears to have some sort of basis under our constitutional scheme itself. Also, the Apex Court did not go into ancient Hindu jurisprudence to examine whether or not such an idea of a public trust ever existed. This would have been more suitable in Indian context.

According to Professor Sax, “three types of restrictions on governmental authority are often thought to be imposed by the public trust doctrine. *Firstly*, the property subject to the trust must not only be used for a public purpose, but it must be held available for use by the general public; *Secondly*, the property may not be sold even for a fair cash equivalent; and *thirdly*, the property must be maintained for particular type of uses.”²³

In *K.M. Chinnappa v. Union of India*,²⁴ the Supreme Court held that “the aesthetic use and the pristine glory cannot be permitted to be eroded for private, commercial or any other use unless the Courts find it necessary, in good faith, for public good and in public interest to encroach upon the said resources.” In *S. Jaganathan* case,²⁵ the Apex Court laid down that the sea- coasts and the beaches are gifts of the nature to the mankind. The aesthetic qualities and recreational utilities of these natural creations have to be maintained at all costs. Therefore, any activity in these areas must pass through strict environmental test and assessment. Such assessment must take into consideration the intergenerational equity and compensation to those who are affected and prejudiced.²⁶ Therefore, in other words, the court has articulated the principle of public trust in a classical manner giving preference to public rights as against developmental activities ignoring environmental assessment. The doctrine of public trust imposes implied restrictions on the power of the government to exploit the natural creations and gifts of nature in the name of development because the government is not the owner of these creations in strict sense of the terms but a trustee. Hence, being a trustee, the government, in the first instance, is under a solemn duty to protect the rights and interests of the people who are the beneficiaries in this context, otherwise, it would amount to breach of public trust.

²² *Dalmia Cement (Bharat) Ltd. v. Union of India*, (1996) 10 SCC 104.

²³ Joseph L. Sax, “Public Trust Doctrine in Natural Resource Law: Effective Judicial Intervention” 68(1) *Michigan Law Review* 473 (1970).

²⁴ AIR 2003 SC 724, 736.

²⁵ (1997) 2 SCC 87.

²⁶ *Ibid.*

In *Nature Lovers' Movement v. State of Kerala*,²⁷ the Kerala High Court has dealt with the doctrine of public trust and pointed out that the Constitution of India while declaring India into a 'sovereign, secular, socialist, democratic republic', has imposed certain obligations on the State. Thus, preservation of ecology, environment and forests is also function of the State and of every citizen. Thus, the use of the land and forests should be for the maximum benefit of the people without causing irreversible damage to the ecology. In this context, it can also be said that Section 2 of the Forest (Conservation) Act, 1980 which prohibits the use of forest land for non-forest purposes and for such use 'prior approval' of the Central Government which is a condition precedent, is a part of the public trust doctrine as the State as a trustee has to manage the natural resources.

In *M. I. Builders Ltd. v. Radhey Shyam Sahu*,²⁸ the Municipal Corporation of Lucknow entered into an agreement with a private builder whereby a park of historical importance that was located in a congested commercial cum residential area was handed over to the builder for the construction of an underground, air-conditioned shopping complex. The case came up in appeal to the Supreme Court from the decision of the High Court. The Apex Court upheld the decision of the High Court. The Apex Court referred to the doctrine of public trust and said that this doctrine would be applicable even in the absence of any statute to nullify the acts of the corporation. As the park is the only open space in the area, the agreement would erode the park's importance. It would lose its quality as a park and trees can no longer be planted here.²⁹ Also, the court noted that the corporation had conducted no study in determining whether or not the complex would have any adverse impact upon the environment. As a result of these factors, the court ruled that the corporation had violated its duty as a trustee in entering into the agreement.³⁰

However, in *Partha Pratim Ghosh v. State of West Bengal*,³¹ the Calcutta High Court did not follow such a rigid stance when a public park was encroached for the development of a shopping centre for the purpose of rehabilitating the hawkers. According to the court, ecological balance and greenery are essential but the need of development of the area cannot be brushed aside.

Though the Supreme Court and the High Courts did not specifically refer to doctrine of public trust directly, in many cases³² they have given effect to this doctrine implicitly. In *People United for*

²⁷ AIR 2000 Ker. 131.

²⁸ (1999) 6 SCC 464.

²⁹ *Id.* at para 50.

³⁰ *Id.* at para 52.

³¹ AIR 2000 Cal. 84, 87.

³² *M.C. Mehta v. Union of India*, AIR 1988 SC 115; *S. Sachidanand Pandey v. State of West Bengal*, AIR 1997 SC 1109; *T. Damodar Rao v. S.O. Municipal Corporation, Hyderabad*, AIR 1987 AP 171; *People United for Better Living in Calcutta v. State of West Bengal*, AIR 1993 Cal. 215.

Better Living in Calcutta v. State of West Bengal,³³ the issue that arose before the Calcutta High Court was with regard to the proposed reclamation of wetland in Calcutta for setting up of a world trade centre. The court granted an injunction against such reclamation and ruled that the State must maintain the wetland in its existing character and not to change it in the name of development. Though this case made no reference to the doctrine, it is clear that the basic principle was applied here to ensure that the wetlands remain in their existing state and are not changed in the name of development.

In *Ganga Pollution case*³⁴, the petitioner filed a writ against the Kanpur Municipalities and other government entities for their failure to prevent wastewater flowing to the river Ganga. As a result of such failure, the river had been polluted heavily and had lost its original character. The Apex Court found that the municipality had failed to fulfill its obligations under various legislations and accordingly directed it to fulfill its duties and prevent any further pollution by increasing the size of the sewers, stop the practice of throwing corpses into the river etc. This case is noteworthy as the Apex Court held that the municipality had certain definite obligations in the maintenance of the river.

In *S. Sachidanand Pandey v. State of West Bengal*,³⁵ the government of West Bengal leased four acres of land belonging to the Calcutta Zoological Garden for the construction of a five star hotel. This lease was challenged before the Calcutta High Court. The court, however, ruled in favor of the hotel. When matter reached before the Apex Court, it was argued that the hotel would disturb the ecological balance, interfere with animals in the zoo and disturb the flight of migratory birds. The Apex Court rejected these contentions and ruled that the government had taken all these factors into mind and had considered all the objections before deciding to grant the lease. Thus, the court refused to interfere with the considered decision of the government. Environmental activists have often criticized this judgment but it is to be noted that the government did in fact considered all the factors. In such circumstances it would be improper for the courts to strike down such a reasoned decision unless it was blatantly unfair. The decision is also in line with the attitude of American Courts in applying the doctrine of public trust wherein, the courts would allow reallocation of resources if it were in the public interest to do so.

³³ AIR 1993 Cal. 215.

³⁴ *M.C. Mehta v. Union of India*, AIR 1988 SC 115.

³⁵ AIR 1997 SC 1109.

In *T. Damodar Rao v. S.O. Municipal Corporation, Hyderabad*,³⁶ a municipal development plan earmarked 150 acres of land for a recreational park. Two public agencies bought 37 acres of these lands to build residential homes and the citizens living around the area challenged this. The court ruled that this was in violation of the development plan. It is pertinent to note that in this case also it was said that concept of private ownership has been eroded by the development of environmental law. This is probably an unwritten reference to the doctrine by the High Court.

In *State of West Bengal v. Kesoram Industries Ltd.*,³⁷ this doctrine was once again followed wherein it was observed that deep underground water belongs to the State in the sense that the doctrine of public trust extends thereto. Ground water is considered as a part of national wealth and it belongs to the entire society. Water is a nectar sustaining life on earth and thus the State has a duty to protect ground water against excessive exploitation. In *M. P. Ramababu v. District Forest Officer*,³⁸ the court held that deep underground soil and water belong to the State in the sense that the doctrine of public trust extends to them. If a person uses his land in such a manner as to pollute the underground water or soil, the State can interfere and prevent contamination even in the absence of a specific law. In *Intellectual Forum v. State of A.P.*,³⁹ the Court held that natural resources which include lakes are held by the State as a trustee of the public, and can be disposed of only in a manner that is consistent with the nature of such a trust.

Hon'ble Justice G. S. Singhvi in *Centre for Public Interest Litigation v. Union of India*,⁴⁰ popularly known as the Radio Spectrum or 2G Spectrum Scam Case, has explained that "Natural resources belong to the people but the State legally owns them on behalf of its people and from that point of view natural resources are considered as national assets, more so because the State benefits immediately from their value... while distributing natural resources, the State is bound to act in consonance with the principles of equality and public trust...".⁴¹ The Court held that air-waves/Spectrum is a natural resource and the State, as a legal owner of these natural resources and as a trustee of the people, has power to distribute them, but "the process of distribution must be guided by the constitutional principles including the doctrine of equality and larger public good."

In resolving the conflict between environment and development, the Court applied the principle of sustainable development which is found in both domestic and international legal instruments.

³⁶ AIR 1987 AP 171.

³⁷ (2004) 10 SCC 201.

³⁸ AIR 2002 AP 256.

³⁹ (2006) 3 SCC 549.

⁴⁰ (2012) 3 SCC 1.

⁴¹ *Id.* at 53.

Furthermore, the principle of intergenerational equity holds a symbiotic relationship with the public trust doctrine, complementing each other. Finally the Court noted Article 48A and 51A of the Constitution as guiding principles to be used in adjudicating upon the matter.⁴²

The facts in *Fomento Resorts and Hotels Ltd. v. Minguel Martins*,⁴³ are comparatively identical to the *Kamal Nath case*. For enlarging the facilities of a hotel with amenities like Yoga centre, a health club and water sports and thus for promoting tourism, the government goes for acquiring the adjoining land. There is a public way used from time immemorial on the land. Laying emphasis upon public duty to maintain public access to the beach without obstruction of any kind, the Supreme Court held that even the provision of an alternative access cannot be accepted as a remedy for depriving the age old rights of the public to pass through the land to a public beach.⁴⁴ None can privatize a public beach by blocking the traditional access. The public trust doctrine, implicit in the agreement for acquisition, commands the government to protect the resources like air, sea, waters and the forests which have such great importance to the public as a whole that it would be wholly unjustified to make them a subject of private ownership.

In *T. N. Godavarman Thirumalpad v. Union of India*,⁴⁵ a fine of rupees one crore was levied by the Supreme Court of India on the State of Himachal Pradesh for not performing its duties as public trustee of the natural resources. As a trustee, the State of Himachal Pradesh was supposed not to grant permission to Pepsi, Coca- Cola and other corporations to damage the ecology and to allow them to write their advertisements on eco- fragile rocks. Since it granted permission to damage ecology of the area by private institutions, it violated its duties as a trustee and protector of the ecosystem which has been provided under Article 48- A of the Constitution of India.

In *Perumatty Grama Panchayat v. State of Kerala*,⁴⁶ the court observed that “it may be within the power of the Panchayat to direct that no more groundwater be extracted on grounds of public policy.” The court analyzed the nature of the water stating that ‘Ground water is a national wealth and belongs to the entire society. It is nectar, sustaining life on earth.’ The court rejected the contention of the respondent that lack of legal constraints on its ability to extract groundwater gives rise to an unfettered right to do so. Despite an absence of rigid legal regulation, the court did not hesitate to rebut this presumption with reference to Principle 2 of the Stockholm Declaration and article 21 of the Indian Constitution, both instruments that hold the environment in great stead. The

⁴² *M. C. Mehta v. Kamal Nath*, (1997) 1 SCC 388.

⁴³ (2009) 3 SCC 571, 600, 601.

⁴⁴ *Id.* at 614.

⁴⁵ 2003 (6) SCALE 374.

⁴⁶ 2004 (1) KLT 731.

Court recounted the decision of the Apex Court in *State of Tamil Nadu v. Hind Stone*,⁴⁷ where the Court held “Rivers, forests, minerals and such other resources constitute a nation’s natural wealth. These resources are not to be frittered away and exhausted by any one generation. Every generation owes a duty to all succeeding generations to develop and conserve the natural resources of the nation in the best possible way. It is in the interest of mankind. It is in the interest of the nation.”

Recognition of this decision is an obvious precursor to the application of the public trust doctrine, which reflects the concern that India has for the environment. The court emphasized previous decisions that make the public trust doctrine a part of the law of India and concluded that water is a common public resource to be protected by the State as trustee for the benefit of public. Notably, the court stressed that an abdication of this duty will necessarily result in an infringement of the rights under Article 21. This case is of interest because of the way in which the public trust doctrine was applied to preserve the groundwater, despite any clear law shaped to deal with groundwater. Over extraction creates an ecological imbalance, posing the risk of converting ecologically fragile lands into deserts.

Thus, we see that relying on the “public trust doctrine” the judiciary in India has tried to protect and preserve forest and natural resources and other component of environment and they tried to enforce the concept of sustainable development to solve the environment- development dilemma.⁴⁸ Each generation is a trustee of environment for succeeding generation. As such every person should strive to maintain the environment for sustained growth in the standard of living.

Public Trust Doctrine: A Part of Principle of Sustainable Development

The concept of sustainable use of natural resources is known to man for centuries. The principle of sustainable development received much recognition after Stockholm Declaration resulting from United Nations Conference on Human Environment of 1972, Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development i.e. *Our Common Future*, popularly known as Brundtland Report and the Earth Summit held at Rio in 1992.

The Brundtland Report defines Sustainable Development as development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of the future generations to meet their own needs. The report emphasizes that sustainable development means an integration of economics and ecology in decision making at all levels. Thus, public trust doctrine can be amalgamated into the concept of sustainable development as ecology is to be preserved by the State and encroachment over ecosystems is permitted only for the benefit of public i.e. for economic development.

⁴⁷ (1981) 2 SCC 205.

⁴⁸ P. Leelakrishnan, *Environmental Law in India* 65 (LexisNexis, Gurgaon, 2016).

Public trust doctrine is an example of ancient dexterity. This doctrine of ancient prodigy is the most comprehensive and prudent among all environmental doctrines. The public trust doctrine is based on the fact that natural resources are a legacy of mankind, their conservation a common concern of all mankind; States are the sole trustees of these natural resources and it is their duty to protect common heritage for the benefit of present and future generations. It is the ostensible affirmation of the fact that management of natural resources, being the administrative responsibility of the State, cannot be delegated to anyone. The doctrine thus serves a twofold function. On the one hand, it preserves the integrated system of sovereign power of the State in protecting this public trust; on the other hand it discharges an environmental mandate, a societal contract and a generational duty of preserving the property as a trust for future generations.⁴⁹

Public trust doctrine has become a significant tool to protect and preserve the natural resources and to manage them properly. It has been recognized as one of the components of the theory of 'sustainable development' which directs the users of natural resources to exploit the resources to satisfy the present needs of the society 'without compromising the ability of the future generations to meet their own needs'. Like the theory of sustainable development, public trust doctrine also aims 'to promote harmony among human beings and between humanity and nature'. Thus, basically the public trust doctrine has been developed and used to protect the natural resources.

It has also been held that 'government has an affirmative duty to administer, protect, manage and conserve fish and wildlife' and thus 'it is a duty attached with the concept of sovereignty'.⁵⁰ The traditional concept of national sovereignty is increasingly defined and modified in the light of newer and significant pragmatic problems we are facing today such as problem of ecological degradation and environmental pollution which may be termed as the problem to managing the commons. Thus, present day nations though are sovereign nations have all powers to rule a country, but it has become very clear that they have certain duties to perform as a welfare State. One of such duties is to manage the commons which has been realized and emphasized time and again. Thus, public trust doctrine in relation to natural environment has recently been recognized as a limitation of the doctrine of sovereignty.

Public trust is a cultural legacy owed to the future generations where government is the trustee and the natural resources are the property and present and future generations are beneficiaries. The public trust doctrine asserts that the government has a fundamental duty to promote and maintain a

⁴⁹ *National Audubon Society v. The Superior Court of Alpine Country*, 658 P. 2d 709 (1983).

⁵⁰ Ed Owens, "For the Good of the People" available at: <http://www.responsiblewildlifemanagement.org/publictrustdoctrine>. (last visited on March 20, 2020).

healthy environment on behalf of the present and future generations. An effective execution of the public trust responsibility requires preventive, remediative and restorative measures. Thus, this doctrine serves the citizenry, including future citizens, by ensuring that the natural environment thrives and will continue to thrive as a healthy and diverse human habitat. It has truly been said that we (the present generation) are the trustees of the representative samples of nature of what we have with us today.

In *Majra Singh v Indian Oil Corporation*,⁵¹ where the petitioner objected to the location of a plant for filling cylinders with liquefied petroleum gas, it was held that the Court can only examine whether authorities have taken all precautions with a view to see that laws dealing with environment and pollution have been given due care and attention. It confirmed that the public trust doctrine has become part of the Indian legal thought processes. The High Court opined that the doctrine is a part and parcel of Article 21 of the Constitution and that there can be no dispute that the State is under an obligation to see that forests, lakes and wildlife and environment are duly protected.

In *N. D. Jayal v. Union of India*,⁵² it has further been explained by the Supreme Court of India that the public trust doctrine is an integral part of the concept of 'sustainable development' and not independent one which means a strategy that caters the needs of the present without negotiating the ability of upcoming generations to satisfy their needs. It was also warned by the Court that the strict adherence to sustainable development is necessary without which the life of coming generations will be in jeopardy. If we read this line in the right perspective, it becomes clear that the present generation and the State are holding the natural resources as public trustee for the posterity. Thus, public trust doctrine is the main edifice of the doctrine of sustainable development. The Court observed: "The strict observance of sustainable development will put us on a path that ensures development while protecting the environment, a path that works for the people and for all generations. It is a guarantee to the present and bequeath to the future."

The application of the doctrine of public trust in suits against private development is common in areas that are rich in resources or environmentally valuable. In *Karnataka Industrial Areas Development Board v. C. Kenchappa*,⁵³ the court identified three principles that can be used to protect ecology i.e. precautionary principle, polluter pays principle and public trust doctrine. A wide interpretation of the doctrine of public trust was taken and it was pointed out that the principle of

⁵¹ AIR 1999 J&K 81.

⁵² AIR 2004 SC 867, 878.

⁵³ AIR 2006 SC 2546.

sustainable development is maintained by the public trust doctrine. The court remained consistent with the approach taken in *M. C. Mehta v. Kamal Nath*,⁵⁴ but is perhaps more insistent that the principle be upheld as an ingredient of sustainable development. Consequently, the court directed that in future, before acquisition of lands for development, the consequence and adverse impact of development on environment must be properly comprehended and the lands be acquired for development that they do not gravely impair the ecology and environment.

C. M. Jariwala, one of the pioneers in the field of environmental law, has rightly observed that articles 48-A and 51A-(g) reflect the ‘principle of intergenerational equity’ and various pronouncements made by the Supreme Court “envisage an emergence of a right of the unborn”.⁵⁵ This right to intergenerational equity and right of unborn to clean environment has emerged from articles 21, 48-A and 51-A (g); and that “existing generation was ordained not to plunder but use nature according to one’s capacity to repay.” Further, “man was simply a trustee of nature for the generations to come and not a grabber who may plunder what he can.” For this we have to make *evi-care* a part of culture, tradition and life conducts.

Limitations of Public Trust Doctrine

Though the public trust doctrine is of recent origin, the courts have indirectly evolved certain restrictions while invoking the doctrine. The Supreme Court has made it clear that the Central Government is always in the position of a trustee in respect of public property. But the use of such a property should not be arbitrary abuse of power, make maladministration and should not amount to unlawful acts causing injury. Because use of such property arbitrarily would amount to betrayal of the trust reposed in the government.⁵⁶

In *Banwasi Sewa Ashram v. State of U.P.*,⁵⁷ the Supreme Court observed that “indisputably, forests are a much wanted natural asset” and it is the State which has to regulate the exploitation of environment (forests) and natural resources and such steps must be taken by the government which do not stand against the concept of sustainable development and environment protection.

While dealing with the environmental issues related to developmental projects the Supreme Court has adopted the public utility approach. It has made it clear that every project of public utility cannot be abandoned but it is necessary to adjust the interest of the people as well as the necessity to maintain the environment. The balance has to be struck between the two interests. The court

⁵⁴ (1997) 1 SCC 388.

⁵⁵ C. M. Jariwala, “Complex Enviro- Techno Science Issues: Judicial Direction”, 42 *Journal of Indian Law Institute* 29 (2000).

⁵⁶ *Common Cause A Registered Society v. Union of India*, AIR 1996 SC 3538.

⁵⁷ AIR 1987 SC 374.

observed that “Where the commercial venture or enterprise would bring in results which are far more useful for the people, the comparative hardship have to be balanced and the convenience and benefit to a large section of the people has to get primacy over comparatively lesser hardship.”⁵⁸

Conclusion

The concept of public trust doctrine which we have borrowed from English law is not a new concept introduced in to our law. The seeds of the doctrine were already present in our laws in terms of natural law, constitutional law, statutory law etc. Preservation of natural resources for benefit of mankind himself is known to man since time immemorial. In order to put seal of law on this concept of preservation, the doctrine of public trust was introduced into our law by the Supreme Court in its landmark judgment of *M. C. Mehta v. Kamal Nath*⁵⁹. Following the American practice the Apex Court has extended the concept of doctrine to all aspects of ecology. The doctrine of *locus standi* has also been diluted in environmental matters.

Now days the doctrine of public trust proves its worth every time where the Courts find that there is no legislation in place for the protection of the interests of the public at large in India. It also guides our Courts in adjudicating the matters where legislation is already in place for the distribution of the resources in a manner so that the rights of the general public over the natural resources remain thoroughly protected. This principle makes our present generation responsible towards the protection of our environment today so that the future generations could enjoy the same rights as ours and further hand over the same ecological environment to many more generations to come in their millennium and beyond.

The concept of public trust doctrine is still a growing concept with blurred boundaries. It has become useful tool in protecting the natural environment and has proved to be very significant tool to develop ecology based real property law of the nation. Still, the primary object of the doctrine is to preserve and protect the things which are common to mankind and make them available in a safe manner to the public for certain public uses.

⁵⁸ 2003 (6) SCALE 374.

⁵⁹ 1996 (9) SCALE 141.

Impact of Right to Information Act, 2005

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“Information is the currency of democracy.”

- Thomas Jefferson

I. Introduction

In the present scenario the knowledge and the transmission of information have been playing an instrumental role in the society for the advancement. Thus, for India, which is one of the biggest democracy in the world it is imperative to provide accountability and transparency in the governance. To achieve this goal, it is necessary that there should be freedom of information to the citizens of the country and this as a right. It is the responsibility of the state. Right to information is inherent in our Constitution in form of Article 19(1)(a) under Fundamental Rights-freedom of speech and expression. It has been held in a number of court judgments including the Supreme Court judgment in the case of *Secretary, Ministry of Information and Broadcasting, Government of India & Ors. v. Cricket Association of Bengal & Anr.*¹ that the freedom of speech and expression includes the right to acquire information and disseminate it. However, as the provision was not explicit and as there was no formal mechanism for seeking information the request for demand for information was rarely entertained sympathetically.

Right to Information Act, 2005 (RTI Act) has been the key to strengthening democracy since its enactment with an objective to make information available for every conscious citizen. In other words, now right to information is a basic necessity of democracy. Right to information can empower all the section of the society to demand and get information about public policies and actions in order to make the government more accountable. It also enables citizens to take part in the decision making process that affect their lives so majorly. Even before the passing of this Act, the legal position with regard to the right to information has been developed through various Supreme Court decisions. After the enactment of the said Act, provisions related to procedure, exemptions, information commissions, etc. has been laid down. Through its elaborate provisions it strengthens the constitutional right to know with the hope that it will change the manner, method and mode of public accountability, transparency and responsibility in the Government of India. This

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¹ [(1995) 2 SCC 161]

Act hailed to be one of the best enactments concerning the peoples right to know and at the same time it puts a check upon the governmental authorities.

II. Impact of Right to Information Act

‘Right to Information’ (RTI) refers to the right of every citizen to retrieve information held by or under the control of public authorities. Information is essential for good governance as it reflects and captures Government activities and processes. It is said that information is the oxygen of democracy.

RTI Act is one of the amiable legislations in India. Plenty number of people has been benefitted from it. No doubt even after the passing of the said Act, the road to accessing information remains difficult to an extent. Still it has greater impact on the system and the people. People are using this Act as an instrument to get their passport, ration card or any other like documents. People from disadvantaged or weaker section are also utilizing this Act to get benefits. This Act had a greater impact on Indian Administration in greater transparency by disclosure of government rules and regulations, maintenance of all records and to be duly indexed in a manner and the form which facilitates the right to information under the Act. The absence of transparency and accountability encourage the government officials to adopt corrupt practices and because of the misuse of power by them there is an environment of distrust between the people and the government. The RTI promotes efficiency in policy making, providing the services and administrative decisions. The efficiency in working of the Government after the passing of the Act must be measured in terms of three facets. First among them is the Administrative efficiency which includes conducting the administrative work without unnecessary delays or ulterior motives. It indicates to the effective management of the system. It comprises of good organization and efficient productivity. This Act has slowly reduced corruption in India.

Corruption Perception Index provided by Transparency International analyze the level of corruption in India and along with the level or position of other countries can be analyzed through ranking and scoring. After the introduction of this Act, India’s ranking in the said list has been reduced considerably.

Right to Information Act, 2005 is playing a crucial role to bring about progress through Openness, Transparency and Accountability in public services delivery systems, authorize the citizens of India from the grass root level and provides a useful instrument for making the functioning of democratic government /public authorities more participatory and meaningful to the governed. The Act is influencing people to come forward and question the progress on various government schemes which creates a positive change in the backward areas and the weaker section of the society. Most

backward sections of rural India are seeking information these days regarding the Prime Minister's Scheme, Mid-day meal etc.

In the present scenario RTI Act is a boon for India which has been witnessing a malignant growth of corruption, lack of public accountability and bureaucratic indifference and numerous other ills. In fact it is Indian judiciary, who has improved the people's right to know as a guaranteed freedom under Articles 19 (1) (a) and 21. **Dr. Y. Padmaja Rant** rightly observed that, "*The attitude of yamdhrumaja is to be recollected in saying 'except the life of your husband'. As the Indian Constitution has not provided any right to the citizens under 'Right to Information', the Indian Judiciary acted cleverly, as Savithri, and interpreted Article 19 (1) (a) and 21 of the Indian Constitution to effect that right to information is indirectly included in these Articles, on the ground that freedom of thought and expression, and freedom to life and personal liberties indirectly includes the right to information and the bill was compelled to be passed in the year 2005.*"² Therefore, the role of Judiciary is laudable for its coherent ruling in favor of the freedom of information or right to information.

III. Conclusion

The RTI Act has been an effective instrument to promote transparency and accountability in administration. However, the objective of the act is yet to be realized at pan India level as there still prevails a glaring lack of awareness and competencies. The misuse of the act by individuals has been a constant source of harassment for the authorities which often results in the disadvantaged groups to be at the receiving end of corrupt practices and subject to no information. Nevertheless of the impending hinderances, it can yet be concluded that right to information is the facet of and underlies all fundamental rights whether it be equality, liberty or any of the six freedoms guaranteed to citizens under the Constitution as also social, economic and political justice referred to in then Preamble to the Constitution because it can act as a check against the misuse of power by those who are constitutionally bound to ensure the realization of those rights. It is now for the public to be alert and watchful of their right to such information and compel disclosure because ultimately it is for them to use this weapon against all public functionaries across the board by ferreting out the truth and fixing accountability.

² Y. Padmaja Rant, "Right to Information: Judicial Approach" Andhra Law Times 2010 (Journal) p. 26

India in transition: Issues and challenges

Dr. Priyaranjan Kumar Shukla*

“A nation grows with the growth of the people, strengthens with the strength and fades away as the nation loses its nationality” said von savigny the propounder of the Historical school of jurisprudence. In my view the above quoted text best introduces the significance of the theme “India in Transition: Issues and challenges”.

According to the author’s perception, the process of transition is a process qualified by a time-phased narrative of aspirations accomplished; of tasks of transformation undertaken in social, economic, political and moral spheres of individual and social life; and of ensuing of a contributory culture and spirituality of values and virtues produced by the people and the state in a hand-in-hand understanding of the purpose of their union.

It is for this reason that the constitution of India in its preamble states, “we the people of India, having solemnly resolved to constitute India into a sovereign socialist secular democratic republic and to secure to all its citizens justice....., liberty....., equality....., fraternity....., in our constituent Assembly on the twenty-sixth day of November, 1949 do.... adopt, enact and give to ourselves this constitution”.

Adopting, enacting and giving the gospel constitution to ourselves was a magnificent evolutionary beginning in the year of 1949. India as a nation has traversed a span of about seventy-one springs and is indeed in the stage of transition.

The author intends to analyze the subject of transition in a way as if a child is to grow but the social conditions within and without the country shape his growth and while he is grown as a mature citizen, his parents are without satisfaction or joy and ask themselves the questions who is/are responsible for the developmental setback? They fumble whether it is owing to the transition “an all subsuming concept” as if man is transformed (drying up of “the self” inclination) and the society is also transformed (an odd-mathematics with which it would not be possible to construct a Triangle or Quadrangle) and the state with law and governance is a helpless witness (albeit it does not mean that state does not govern but the problems surfacing for governance before it are somewhat

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peculiar, queer and as if dancing steps in state of debauchery. The state is under compulsion to consider such situations as transitional but it is a matter of deep research whether such transitions are spontaneous or non-spontaneous or maneuvered. Spontaneous transition is a good concept in the social vocabulary but the latter finds reference in the thesaurus of delinquents and delinquency only. In between the two ranges- spontaneous and non-spontaneous transformations state adopts the practice of appraising and honoring acts and persons for their national services.

In the author's view the subject "India in transition" can best be divided into three parts for intensive as well as extensive analysis. The three parts are Man, society and 'The Self'. The term requires intended specific significations which are as follows: -

1. Man: - For a country, man is the most valuable resource. In terms of transition man would be forced to be adopting globalization means and may for a moment be very happy, even more jealous to possess things, attributes, tastes and temperaments. In other words, imitation instincts weave into cognizance and become nature of the concerned man. It is a precarious situation of station of human life and must be required to be guarded by Man, Society and State so that man is not uprooted from the place of his/her birth. In other words, cravings and longings for our land, our language, our culture and our way-of-life must be grown to be fastened in the blood-stream. In this regard, the first issue emerging is how to contain himself for a man inwardly so that he is happy, law abiding and virtually prosperous and can contribute to integrity and sovereignty? Let Indianness be the goal to be achieved by every human being in his relative skill-scale and potential so that one is not a loser or gainer rather participator or actor for the cause of Indianness.

This issue poses challenges and at the outset the author submits that challenges can be effectively addressed by society at large i.e. by institutions like family, educational institutions, public offices as well as the state. It is therefore essential that the cornerstone principles and practices of Indianness i.e. oneness in thought, word and action be determined and emphasized to be followed by every stakeholder referred as above as man, family, educational institution, public offices as well as the state. Rights and individualism have been so far prescribed and provided by the constitution and laws but now it is the most urgently called for issue that an intensive programmschrift be devised for professing, practicing and propagating the duty for strengthening Indianness in thought, word and action. It is not the author's intention that Indian should be an untouchable at the plank of globalized World, rather the idea is let the Indianness be not uprooted in terms of its cultural

heritage and in sway of progressiveness foreign dangerous elements be permitted to become human cosmetics.

The issue of human counterpart of the cosmic existence and its contribution with respect to Indianness stands for maintaining ethical and moral virtues for man to man and for man to society so that man is the best friend of the other man and humanity as well as is one and united for the nation.

This idea will require the following aspects to be researched qualitatively as well as quantitatively in the ancient Indian literature of immortality.

- (1) Determining definition, nature, scope and function of oneness to be adopted by every stakeholder in respective work plan, e.g. by family, neighborhood, society, social institutions and the state.

The present task is arduous and requires continuous interaction and evaluation amongst stakeholders on a periodic basis so that necessary alterations and additions can be made on the basis of experiences.

Family is the first nursery of rights for a man, educational institutes are the role-modelers and therefore if there is a cooperative consensus about definition, nature and scope of Indianness for the peerless progress of the child, that would be the best contribution for shaping the governance at public offices and higher levels. In author's view progress of the mankind is for spiritual enlightenment which is across the religious dictates and doctrines but always for the service of the humanity as is referred to in the Parable of the Good Samaritan in the third testament of the Bible.

It deserves mention here that in educational institutions imparting professional education, the totality of the focus is towards grabbing high-salary/ perks avocations and students at the end of their Course turn out to be overall a mechanized mind. That is really a problem beset with worries not only for the present but also for the future of the country. The end product of the professionally educational institutions as referred above due to high tuition fee and other necessary expenses which are not within reach of poor persons howsoever talented they may be; costs the nation and society exorbitantly and therefore it becomes the first and foremost duty of state to establish adequate number of educational institutions to provide best quality of education at par with the existing

private institutions at prices affordable by everyone. This problem's other side relates to the mindset-training during years of studies by the students of the professional institutions charging exorbitant fees wherein, needless, to say, that mindset is centered around selfishness in respect of competing, defeating and winning for the self. There are persons who fail to perform and win over others. The education system should be therefore reformed. Apart from providing skillful training to all students, meritorious selflessness should be the ideal to win by every student professional. Then only, Indianness in true sense can be stated to have been contributed by the education system.

In the background of the above thought it is the author's call to every stakeholder of the educational institution i.e. 'Teachers, Taught, Institution and The self' to unite and contribute for national integrity, peace and prosperity as their rhythm of life, and sustenance; wherein 'The Self' is all without and against selfishness and is but for human service.

- (2) Society is the second important part of country, for the purpose of this write-up contextually warranted. Nevertheless, it is to be accepted that societal initiatives are very important for maintaining man happy and disciplined so that he does not commit crimes. Various explanations are attempted by criminologists of different times as to how a man commits a crime and one of the various theories of causation of crimes is known as control theory which emphasizes that if societal forces and initiatives are sufficiently available to a prospective offender in such a manner that he is contained in himself, he will generally not commit crime!

At this context it is not out of validity to state that the issue touching upon man from corners of society is his anxiety for being safe and free from victimization. This is why the current thought in province of criminology is that rights are not as important as safety and security for human being. The problem and challenge is acute for girls and women who are sexually ravished, raped, gangraped and ultimately murdered. It is, therefore, urgently called that humanity should find an answer and solution to the crime problem.

The following are some of the top important and top urgent issues and challenges of the present Indian society. (i.e. India in transition)

- (i) The rising sexual crimes against girls and women.

- (ii) The apathy of people (victims specifically) in criminal justice system on account of delayed justice. The Nirbhaya case is the recent befitting example.
- (iii) Maintenance and welfare of parents and senior citizens-it is a sad commentary on the existence of a familial/social bondage when parents and senior citizens are evicted by their sons, daughters and in laws from their houses and are illtreated and assaulted. The Maintenance and Welfare of Parents and Senior Citizens Act 2007 has been recently amended by the Parliament to take stern action against delinquent sons and daughters who inherit the property but do not discharge their obligations.

(iv) Time has come when intellectual and physical emancipation must be thought to be provided to household womenfolk who are confined from kitchen to main gate of the house throughout their lives and are not beneficiaries in the intellectual, physical and spiritual respects. Woman is the most precious but scarce resource of a society and it is therefore important that every womenfolk of the country irrespective of her rural or urban station of life must be accorded due respect to an extent that she finds himself physically, intellectually and spiritually advanced. Physical advancement here stands for material prosperity so that women do not suffer from vicious circle of dispossessions inviting moral squalor. How to accomplish the emancipation of household womenfolk is a challenging task and in this regard the author would submit a view that the task can be completed looking into the respective societies and conditions of women.

(v) Removal of migration of labourers from villages to the cities is a major issue of our country and the schemes initiated by the governments have indeed been boons but the practice of migration has still continued as against the objectives of the schemes.

What would lure the labourers to embrace their native places, make them happy to work and not to migrate to cities is a big challenge to address for the country (India in transition).

(vi) Literacy of female poor girls must be attended on priority in villages as well as cities. The author has witnessed the poor girls working at construction sites along with their family members and they make out the fittest cases for call from the society whither a girl in tender age is not a person worth dignity the society and state should safeguard!

(vii) The unorganized labour sector is the other biggest issue of India in transition, which requires to be dealt not only by state and law but also by the society at large. Willem Bonger, a noted philosopher rightly says that civilizations across the world are contributed by labourers who are not paid their due.

Let the development plans of the country imbibe the anxiety expressed by Willem Bonger and launch the practice of paying the labourers their rights over due.

There are a large number of important issues and challenges on the social fronts of the country (India in transition), out of which, in brief, some of the most important subject matters can be submitted as follows: -

- a) Female foeticide
- b) Prenatal sex-selection
- c) Discrimination between male and female child
- d) Child marriage and marriage against choice (specially on behalf of girl)
- e) Eradication of social evils of witchcraft and gods Manship in some parts of the country where wild justice of lynching is granted to the witch as well as family members.

In addition to the above there are innumerable local evil practices of society in India. They require to be dealt with by local governments as well as other prudent and intelligent persons. In this context, there is a famous adage of jurisprude Emile Durkheim that “as the society grows from pre-modern to modern stage, there is to come a situation of anomie(normlessness) wherein man does not know what to do and where to go. He is utterly confused and frustrated.”

The author would submit that let there be no development or modernization or globalization that turns out to be a blind race of disowning Indianness and owning all parasitic possessions of mind and action! In other words, for example, no deforestation for the lust of industries and smart cities! Lest it is too late, the country should awake and think over with concerted actions with rhythm of “NO” to so many things.

3. ‘The self’ parameter of this discourse depicts a human tangent touching upon man, society and the process of governance i.e. state. Afterall, state is the embodiment of popular wishes and voices. In relation to man, society and state ‘The self’ coefficient is of paramount significance. The ‘self’

has already been referred above, but in respect of state it stands for the following challenging issues: -

(i) corruption-free governance.

(ii) Zero tolerance to crime in all stages of governance including election process of every kind.

(iii) Transparency in administration with maximum permissible grant to right to know.

(iv) Right to recall the elected representatives on grounds of disloyalty/ violation of 'The Self'.

(v) Supply of essential services like food and civil supplies, medical facilities, and educational institutions to cater to needs of population fairly and equitably.

(vi) To safeguard the interests of vulnerable sections of humanity e.g. Homeless beggars, aged and sick persons suffering from serious diseases on pro bono basis.

(vii) Last but not the least, to act, envision and act as a visionary and saviour for the growth of human progeny irrespective of times and challenges of crises.

It is a great challenge for the persons of authority to be devoid of the temptations of selfishness but Indian history encloses several great names like the father of the nation, Shri M.K. Gandhi (Bapu), Pt. Jawahar Lal Nehru, Dr. Rajendra Prasad, Pt. Madan Mohan Malviya, Dr.Hari Singh Gour, Shri Ravindranath Tagore and several others to name few who had sacrificed their selfishness for the cause of humanity and service of the people which India, on the day, should follow against the otherwise commonsense and commonplace acknowledgement by the people of India, as just the reverse in respect of the large chunk of governance.

Gender Justice in Secular India : A comparative study

Mayank Kumar*

According to the census 2001 women constitute half the population of the society. From the vedic culture it is presumed that the women are the best creation of God .

'यत्र नार्यस्तु पूज्यन्ते रमन्ते तत्र देवता: i.e. The Lord lies where the women worshipped . It means that all the prosperity belong to the well being of the women . But it is a harsh reality that women have been ill-treated in every society for ages and India is no exception. We have been gifted with a history of discrimination, subjugation and suppression. India is a country of rich customs, traditions. And people of various faith and religions are living in India .most of the people of India follows the religion in their personal laws. "India is a country which abounds in personal laws and each community has its own personal law."1 The freedom of religion and equality are the fundamental rights given to the citizens of India but in the patriarchy society women has been given second status. This work makes an effort to realize the need of the hour in advancing gender justice through the social media, political parties judiciary, by using various mechanisms and could serve as an inspiring model for other countries of the world

Key words:vedic culture , नारितस्य. , पूज्यन्ते,रमन्ते, देवता, society, customs, traditions, religions, personal laws , freedom , equality, patriarchy society, status, gender justice, social media, political parties , judiciary, mechanisms, countries, world.

In India, it is assumed that during vedic period women enjoyed an equal status as of men. The Upanishads and the Vedas have cited women sages and seers. But afterwards the position of women considerably declined . Sati Pratha and child marriage creates gender imbalance in Indian Society. Later on Sati Pratha and child marriage banned through legal reform. But now a days domestic violence, trafficking, dowry deaths, female infanticide, female foeticide, sexual offences , violence and sexual harassment at work place becomes major problem in the society. In the patriarchy society women are deprived of dignity , economic resources . They are dependent on men for their living , confined to domestic arena , do all house hold unpaid works. In modern times many women are supporting men in work field in many areas like education , nursing , communication etc as

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well as with the domestic responsibility . Even though they are considered to be less productive than their counterpart. Her general status in the family and in the society has been recognized. as second status. With the development of society and the shift from subsistence to a market economy have had a dramatic negative impact on women, cutting them out of employment due to unskilled and lack of education. Child labour among girls and unequal wages for women for similar work are common. Working women of all segments of society face various forms of discrimination. Females are under the clutches of numerous evils such as discriminations, oppressions, violence, within the family, at the work places and in the society. In order to improve the condition of women in India, Legislature enacted the large volume of enactments and many of these legislations were enacted: Abolition of Sati Act, 1829; Widow Remarriage Act, 1856; Child Marriage Restraint Act, 1929; Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961; etc ,The Workmen Compensation Act, 1923; Payment of Wages Act, 1936; Factories Act, 1948; Maternity Benefit Act, 1961; Minimum Wages Act, 1948; Employees State Insurance Act 1948 and Pensions Act, 1987; etc.

India is a secular country and freedom of religion is the fundamental right of the citizen of the India whereas Gender injustice is a problem in secular India . Therefore a country with a secular constitution such as India is expected to uphold religious freedom as well as social justice.

What does Gender Justice means :

Gender justice is an undefined terminology. Sometimes it refers to equal treatment of both men and women and sometimes 'justice to the fairer sex'. However, for the purpose of this work gender justice will be treated as the 'justice to the fairer sex'. It is an important essence of a civilised society. No society can progress denying gender justice. Our father of nation Mahatma Gandhi once said, "Women are the companion of men, gifted with equal mental capacity. Ignoring them will be a big mess for the civilization." In most ancient societies women have been considered men's inferiors physically and intellectually. Marriages were arranged; women had no property rights and were not entitled to education. According to Hindu laws of Manu, as put forth in the Manusmriti, women were subservient to male relatives. Widow-remarriage was not allowed and the law sanctioned the practice of Sati, a truly atrocious practice. Wearing bangles is also understood to be a form of fetters/shackles. Under common law of England, a married woman hardly had any rights; she had no rights to her property after marriage"²". NyamuMusembi, a fellow at the Institute of Development Studies at the University of Sussex, sums up this concept of gender justice as under: "Gender justice is about more than simply questioning the relationship between men and women. It involves crafting strategies for corrective action toward transforming society as a whole to make it more just and equal; and it means a place in which women and men can be treated as

fully human. Moreover, it implies moving away from arbitrary to well-reasoned, justifiable and balanced that is, 'fair social relations'."3" There are some key elements of gender justice that are similar in all around the globe and need to be rectified. "4"

1. Fair treatment of women and men, where fairness is evaluated on the basis of substantive outcomes and not on the basis of a notion of formal equality that use an implied 'sameness' standard. This means that in some cases, different treatment may be what is needed for a just outcome.

2. Fairness should be at the level of interpersonal relations and at the level of institutions that mediate these relations and offer redress for wrongs.

3. Acknowledgement that given a long history of gender hierarchy that has disadvantaged women, gender justice inevitably implies realigning the scales in women's favour.

4. Questioning the arbitrariness that characterizes the social construction of gender.

Gender Justice in Secular India

The Preamble to our Constitution declare that India is a secular state. " A secular state should not be taken as anti – religion state. "5" A secular state is a state which is neutral in religious matters .Therefore It declares the equal treatment to all religions .Therefore the detailed provisions for gender justice have been provided in the Constitution of India , given below. "WE, THE PEOPLE OF INDIA....." the golden words of preamble includes men and women of all castes, religions, etc. It wishes to render "Equality of status and of opportunity" to every men and women. The Preamble again assures "dignity of individuals" which includes the dignity of women. The Constitution of India has various provisions to ensure equality of the sexes and also to dismantle the prevalent imbalances in gender hierarchy. Article 14 of the Constitution provides for equality before the law and equal protection of the law. Article 15 safeguards the right against discrimination. The Constitution also provides for positive discrimination and affirmative action on some counts. Article 15(3) permits special provisions for women. Article 16 provides equal opportunity with respect to public employment and they shall not be discriminated on the basis of sex of the person. Article 21 guarantees the right to life, the interpretation which has been broadened to include the right to live with dignity. Article 23 guarantees the right against exploitation and also prohibits traffic in human beings. The Directive Principles of policies contained in Part IV of the Constitution of India guide the states formulation and administration of laws and policies and are "fundamental in the governance of the country"6". They instruct the state to secure and protect a social order in which social, economic, and political justice. "7" Directive Principles relevant to gender justice in general and for this dissertation in particular are the

directions to the government “to eliminate inequalities in status, facilities and opportunities” contained in Article 39(a); “to ensure that the legal system promote justice ,on the basis of equal opportunity” contained in Article 39A; “to secure just and humane conditions of work and maternity relief” contained in Article 42; “equal pay for equal work for both men and women” contained in Article 39(d) and reinforced by the Equal Remuneration Act, 1975; “to ensure that the “health and strength of workers, men and women are not abused” contained in Article 39(e); “to secure for its citizens a uniform civil code throughout the territory of India” contained in Article 44 and “to regard the improvement of nutrition, standard of living and public health” contained in Article 47 of our Constitution as its primary duties among others.”⁸ Article 51A(e) provides that, it shall be the duty of every citizen of India to promote harmony and the spirit of common brotherhood amongst all the people of India transcending religious, linguistic and regional or sectional diversities; to renounce practices derogatory to the dignity of women. Thus, it clearly indicates that it is the fundamental duty of every Indian to respect women. But the freedom of religion curtail all the rights of women.

Efforts of Parliament for Gender Justice-

The Parliament has succeeded in its efforts to provide for reservation of seats for women in elections to the Panchayats and the Municipalities. Reservations of seats for women in Panchayats and Municipalities have been provided in Article 243D and 243T of the Constitution of India. According to Article 243D(3), “not less than onethird, (including the number of seats reserved for women belonging to the Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes) of the total number of seats to be filled up by direct election in every Panchayat, shall be reserved for women and such seats may be allotted by rotation to different constituencies in a Panchayat. Article 243T(3) of the Constitution provides similar provisions for reservation of seats for women in direct election in the Municipalities. Today, we observe a shift towards the service sector by working women but no occupational field is impervious to gender injustice as of today. It is also worth mentioning to note that there is also a statutory enactment in India against sexual harassment at work place¹⁹ confirming the Supreme Court guidelines pertaining to sexual harassment at the work place in the landmark case of Vishakha v. State of Rajasthan “9”. In India, women are entitled to maternity benefits under the Maternity Benefit Act, 1961 which provides a 90 day paid leave. Women do not have a right to Abortion in India. The Medical Termination of Pregnancy Act, 1971 legalizes abortion only in certain circumstances. There is no provision in the Act which allows abortion on the basis of the will of the woman. Section 312 of the Indian Penal Code, 1860, defines the offence of ‘causing miscarriage’. It states that whoever voluntarily causes a woman with child to miscarry

shall, if not in good faith, shall be punished with imprisonment of up to 3 years or fine or both. A woman who causes herself to miscarry is within the scope of this Section. The Domestic Violence Act, 2005 has been enacted by the Parliament to curb the onslaught of domestic violence. It is the first of its kind in India. An important advance made by the Act in understanding the nature of domestic violence has been in the combination of civil and criminal remedies. The number of cases of domestic violence in India is on the rise. This may also be due to greater reporting of Domestic Violence Cases. However, a great majority of Sexual assaults go unreported. Rape is a perverse form of subjugation of women by men. It is a crime of violence, not sex primarily. Some scholars opine that the Indian Law on rape is gender biased and male oriented. Gender neutral rape laws in India have been also acted upon¹⁰. Commercial sex work i.e. the exchange of sexual services for money is legal in India but related activities such as soliciting in public places, owing a brothel, and pimping are illegal. The primary law dealing with sex workers is the Immoral Traffic (Suppression) Act, 1956. However, male prostitution is not recognized in the Indian law. Another oppressive tradition of giving dowry has been abolished by the Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961, which imposes stiff fines and minimum imprisonment of 5 years in prison for violation. There are also provisions for at least one women member in various statutory committees in India like; National Judicial Appointment Commission, National Human Rights Commission, National Commission for Schedule Cast, National Commission for Schedule Tribe, Consumer Redressal Forum etc.

However, despite of such holistic approach by the legislators we are not able to create a women friendly society in India. Supreme Court's Chief Justice P Sathasivam (as he then was) aptly remarked that exploitation of women is a "reality" in India and gender justice a "fragile myth", attributing the evil to social prejudices. He also observed that the discrimination against women stems not from legislative insufficiency, but can be attributed to the deep-rooted social values and ethics involved in the establishment of Indian society.¹¹

CONCLUSION:

The Indian judiciary develops its own theory of gender justice, informed by local realities and universally accepted norms. Women's rights activist and the Supreme Court plays a critical role in shaping the discourse. Through various mechanisms, the Court has broadly addressed human rights abuses and spurred the other branches of government into action. However, judicial directives that trespass too deeply into the realms of the legislature and the executive can ultimately undermine the Court's powers, especially when its orders cannot be effectively implemented. The Court could avoid these problematic tendencies by maintaining a focused loyalty to the Constitution. Having generously empowered the judiciary to develop the procedurally flexible PIL mechanism, the

Indian Constitution provides a strong legal basis to enforce gender justice through this process, and permits guidance from international law to that end. Moreover, the Constitution has clearly delineated the roles of each branch of government, and the judiciary must respect these boundaries in order to maintain its own legitimacy and credibility. A country with a secular constitution such as India is expected to uphold religious freedom as well as social justice. Therefore the successful promotion of gender justice also depend on greater coordination and mobilization of social activist, organizations , NGO's creating social awareness under the rule of law.

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Co-operative Banks and the new roadmap for recovery of Non-Performing Assets in India

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Abstract

Recovery of Non-Performing Assets widely referred to as NPAs is tantamount for any Banking and Financial Institution because unless the loan repayment is not forth coming the Banking and Financial Institutions can't run their businesses and often run into losses. In case the repayment is not coming for any reason whatsoever, the account turns into NPA and Banking and Financial Institutions have all the right to recover as an institutional creditors. In India, however there has been debate and challenge with respect to the means of recovery of NPAs by Co-operative banks and the RBI notification which made the provisions of Securitisation and Reconstruction of Financial Assets and Enforcement of Securities Interest Act, 2002 (also known as the SARFAESI Act) applicable to Co-operative banks was challenged before the apex court. The landmark 5 judges bench judgment of the Hon'ble Apex court has made the provisions of the act applicable to the Co-operative banks, thereby easing the recovery procedures for Co-operative Banks in India, which otherwise are suffering from lack of revenue and burden of bad loans. The paper deals with the impact of the judgment on the recovery mechanism of the Co-operative banks and the future ahead.

Keywords:- Co-operative Society, creditors, Non-Performing Assets

Introduction

The history of Co-operative banks in India dates back to 1904 when in order to tackle the problem of rural credit there was an advent of the Co-operative movement leading to the passage of Co-operative Societies Act. At present, Co-operative banks play a very crucial role in rural financing for sectors under agriculture, livestock, milk, personal finance, self-employment, setting up of small-scale units etc. The Co-operative banks provides for a solution for the ages old debt trap of money lenders by providing financial credit recognized by law. The Co-operative banks work on Co-operative basis and belong to their members.

The Co-operative Banks are registered under the States Co-operative Societies Act and are regulated by the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) under the Banking Regulations Act, 1949, and the Banking Laws (Co-operative Societies) Act, 1955. According to an RBI report¹, at the end of March 2019, credit cooperatives comprised 1,544 urban co-operative banks (UCBs) and 96,248 rural co-operative banks (end-March 20181), with the latter accounting for 64.7 per cent of the total assets of co-operatives.

Some of the salient features of a Co-operative bank in India are:-

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¹https://rbidocs.rbi.org.in/rdocs/Publications/PDFs/05CHPT5_24122019878A5AF64EB74900B7AD6FF7093EE45F.PDF (Accessed 13 May, 2020 03:43AM)

- a. Owned and controlled by the members;
- b. A significant part of the profit can also be distributed to the Co-operative members, with legal and statutory limitations;
- c. Aim at financial inclusion i.e. taking banking to the doors of marginalized population

The Co-operative banks have always been in news in India for some reason or the other. Last year the financial crisis and limitation on the withdrawal by the depositors of Punjab and Maharashtra Co-operative Bank stirred the debate around the Dual Regulation of Co-operative Banks in India. The whole debate pointed towards few shortcomings and problems faced by the Co-operative Banks in India which was leading towards the dilution and merger. One of such major problems faced by the Co-operative Banks in India is with respect to the recovery of Bad loans or the Non-Performing Assets.

The whole process of recovery of NPAs by Co-operative Banks can be studied in light of the Hon'ble Supreme Court's Constitution Bench judgement in the most recent case of *Pandurang Ganpati Chaugule and Ors. V. Vishwarao Patil Murgud Sahakari Bank Ltd.*² which upheld the RBI notification dated 28th January 2003 issued under the Banking Regulation Act, 1949, that brought Co-operative banks within the class of "banks" under the Act by virtue of Section 2(1)(c)(v) of the SARFAESI Act, 2002 wherein Central Government may notify any Bank. The Apex court further stated that the Co-operative banks involved in banking activities are covered u/s 5(c)³ & 56(a)⁴ of the Banking Regulation Act, 1949 meaning that the Co-operative banks shall fall within the purview of Section 2(1)(c)(i) of the Securitisation and Reconstruction of Financial Assets and Enforcement of Securities Interest Act, 2002 (also known as the SARFAESI Act) which defines Bank as under:-

² <https://indiankanoon.org/doc/156404699/> (Accessed 13 May 2020 02:46 AM)

³ Section 5(c) Banking Regulation Act,1949- Banking company means any company which transacts the business of banking in India. Explanation.—Any company which is engaged in the manufacture of goods or carries on any trade and which accepts deposits of money from the public merely for the purpose of financing its business as such manufacturer or trader shall not be deemed to transact the business of banking within the meaning of this clause;

⁴ Section 56 Banking Regulation Act,1949- Act to apply to co-operative societies subject to modifications. — The provisions of this Act, as in force for the time being, shall apply to, or in relation to, co-operative societies as they apply to, or in relation to banking companies subject to the following modifications, namely:—

(a) throughout this Act, unless the context otherwise requires,—

(i) references to a "banking company" or "the company" or "such company" shall be construed as references to a co-operative bank;

(ii) references to "commencement of this Act" shall be construed as references to commencement of the Banking Laws (Application to Co-operative Societies) Act, 1965 (23 of 1965);

Section 2 (c) bank" means-

- (i) a banking company; or
- (ii) a corresponding new bank; or
- (iii) the State Bank of India; or
- (iv) a subsidiary bank; or
- (v) such other bank which the Central Government may, by notification, specify for the purposes of this Act;

By virtue of the judgment a Co-operative Bank has been brought within the purview of “*Secured Creditor*” under the provisions of Section 2(zd) of the SARFAESI Act, 2002.

Recovery Procedure under the SARFAESI Act, 2002

Once the Apex court has upheld the application of the SARFAESI Act, 2002 to the Co-operative banks, the recovery may be initiated by the banks as per the provisions of the act which aims at time bound and without court intervention recovery of the NPAs. The step by step recovery procedure under SARFAESI Act, 2002 is as under :-

- i. On stamping of Advances as NPA as per RBI guidelines, the notice u/s 13(2) of the captioned Act is issued to all the borrowers which includes the guarantors and mortgagors.⁵

It is noteworthy here that the NPA classification is borrower wise and not facility wise i.e. once a facility granted to a borrower is classified as NPA, the other facilities of the same borrower under same CIF shall automatically be classified as NPA even if the repayment is regular in other facilities.

- ii. In the said notice clear 60 days notice is to be given to the recipient of the notice and for reckoning of 60 days the date of receipt of notice is considered. In case the notice is not delivered to the borrower due to wrong address or any such reason, the said notice is to be published in two newspapers (One essentially vernacular). From the date of publication of notice 60 days is reckoned. As per the act if any objection to the notice under Section 13(2) is raised by the borrower in writing then the same is to be replied with 15 days of the receipt of the objection⁶.

⁵ Section 2(f) SARFAESI Act, 2002- “borrower” means any person who has been granted financial assistance by any bank or financial institution or who has given any guarantee or created any mortgage or pledge as security for the financial assistance granted by any bank or financial institution and includes a person who becomes borrower of a asset reconstruction company consequent upon acquisition by it of any rights or interest of any bank or financial institution in relation to such financial assistance or who has raised funds through issue of debt securities;

⁶ Section 13 (3A) SARFAESI Act, 2002 - If, on receipt of the notice under sub-section (2), the borrower makes any representation or raises any objection, the secured creditor shall consider such representation or

- iii. After completion of 60 days the Authorized Officer alongwith the Recovery team is free to proceed for taking possession of the secured interest. However, as a way of extra caution notice u/s 13(4) of the Act is given indicating date, time and place of the possession.
- iv. On the date and time mentioned in the notice under Section 13(4) of the act, the Authorized Officer along with the Recovery team proceeds to take the possession. In case the possession is given willingly then the Physical possession is taken and notice about the same is published in two newspapers (one essentially vernacular). If the possession is resisted by the owner of the property then symbolic possession of the same is taken and notice about the same is published in two newspaper (one essentially vernacular). Be it physical or symbolic possession, as a matter of practice the whole incident is to be recorded in camera and inventory is to be prepared.
- v. If the possession is physical then the e-auction notice is published in two newspapers (one essentially vernacular) and the auction is carried out in e-auction mode as per Finance Ministry guidelines by giving mandatory 30 days notice. The e-auction notice should be uploaded on the government website www.etenders.gov.in for better transparency and in addition to this the said 30 days notice is to be sent to the borrowers⁷. After successful bidding the sale certificate is to be registered in the name of successful bidder.
- vi. In case the possession is symbolic then the application under 14 of the Act is to be filed before the CMM/DM as the case may be. On receiving the permission from CMM/DM the physical possession of the property is to be taken with the help Police and personnel as authorized by the CMM/DM. At this stage by virtue of Supreme Court directives in *Harshad Govardhan Sondagar v. International Assets Reconstruction Co. Ltd. & Ors.*⁸ and *Vishal N Kalsaria v. Bank of India*⁹ while passing order for possession the interest of the tenants of such properties is to be taken into consideration as provisions of SARFAESI Act, 2002 can't be considered as having overriding effects over the tenancy laws.

objection and if the secured creditor comes to the conclusion that such representation or objection is not acceptable or tenable, he shall communicate 3[within fifteen days] of receipt of such representation or objection the reasons for non-acceptance of the representation or objection to the borrower:

Provided that the reasons so communicated or the likely action of the secured creditor at the stage of communication of reasons shall not confer any right upon the borrower to prefer an application to the Debts Recovery Tribunal under section 17 or the Court of District Judge under section 17A.

⁷ Rule 8 (6) of the Security Interest Enforcement Rules, 2002

⁸ (2014) 6 SCC 1

⁹ (2016) 3 SCC 762

In cases the property mortgaged to the Banks or Financial Institution is occupied by tenants then by simple notice the rent payable to the owner can also be attached by the Banks or Financial Institution.¹⁰

- vii. Once the physical possession is taken with the assistance of the CMM/DM the same procedure of publication of sale notice is followed and property is handed over to the successful bidder.

At any of the stages as mentioned above, if the defaulter clears the outstanding dues then account may be standardized by Bank or the Financial institution. It is critical to note here that if Banks or financial institution errs in following any of the mandatory steps as listed in the Security Interest Enforcement Rules, 2002 the complete action shall be void *ab initio* and the whole process has to be carried out again.

In addition to the above mentioned steps under SARFAESI Act, 2002 the secured creditor can take over the management of the defaulter.¹¹

The SARFAESI Act, 2002 also facilitates incorporation of Special Purpose Vehicles viz. Asset Reconstruction Company which are governed by RBI and are termed as Secured Creditor for the purpose of the act¹². These Companies can purchase the NPAs and carry out all the above mentioned procedure just like any other Secured creditor.

Though SARFAESI was enacted with special purpose of expediting recovery of bad loans, it has failed to achieve its aim because of less number of Debt Recovery Tribunal and pendency of large number of cases in them. Secondly, physical possession is practically difficult in many a cases because of reluctance of the borrowers and tenancy issues leading to failure of the whole SARFAESI action.

Other than initiating recovery under the SARFAESI Act, 2002 the Co-operative banks may also exercise other options as listed under:-

a. Legal Notice

The Legal Notice calling for the outstanding dues or recalling the complete advance can be issued from the Branch level itself depending upon the discretion of the Branch head. This might help in recovery as usually the borrowers of a Co-operative bank are people from the common mass with eggshell skull who are afraid of legal actions and notices. Here Co-operative banks have an edge

¹⁰ Section 13 (4)(d) SARFAESI Act, 2002

¹¹ Section 15 of SARFAESI Act, 2002

¹² Section 2(zd) of SARFAESI Act, 2002

over other Banks and Financial institutions as their defaulting borrowers are usually corporate borrowers who at times don't even take note of such notices.

b. By Filing Legal Suit

Before the enactment of SARFAESI Act, 2002 the only legal recourse available with the Institutional creditors was filing of civil suits. Based on the premises that every credit related transaction is based on contractual obligation, the money suit was filed before the Civil Courts as per the Civil Procedure Code, 1908. With the increase in number of defaults it became practically impossible for the already over-burdened and less in number existing Civil Courts to adjudicate the matter leading to large number of pendency. After recommendation of various committees like Tiwari Committee, the "High Level Committee" headed by V.S. Hegde and specifically Committee on Financial Systems headed by Shri M. Narasimham, former Governor of Reserve Bank of India, Parliament enacted The Recovery of Debts Due to Banks and Financial Institutions Act, 1993 (DRT Act) by virtue of which specialized Tribunals called as Debt Recovery Tribunals were set-up to adjudicate upon cases with default of Rs. 10 Lakhs and above, for lesser amount the jurisdiction still lies with the regular Civil Courts. The Banks or the Financial institution to whom any due is payable by the borrower can make an application under Section 19 of the said Act. The Act gives a phased and time-bound manner for adjudication of claim by the Banks or Financial institution the darkening fact is that the due to number of cases and stays from higher courts DRTs which were supposed to be specialized Tribunal for Debt recovery have become more or less like regular Civil Courts.

Shortcomings of SARFAESI Act, 2002 vis-à-vis recovery by Co-operative banks

Undoubtedly, the judgment will have an impact on the recovery mechanism of the Co-operative banks and will confer the quasi-judicial powers under the SARFAESI Act, 2002 on the Authorized Officer of the Bank initiating such action, however, there are certain aspects which still need to be addressed as under

1. Before the judgment of Hon'ble Apex court in *Pandurang Ganpati Chaugule and Ors. V. Vishwarao Patil Murgud Sahakari Bank Ltd.* the Co-operative banks were empowered to recover outstanding loans through the mechanism provided in the respective State Co-operative laws, which are comprehensive, self-contained and less expensive remedy provided the banks have put in place a proper mechanism. For instance Section 101 of Maharashtra Co-operative Societies act 1960 confers on the Registrar of Societies, the power of a Special Court having jurisdiction to pass a money decree. Usually, the Co-operative society is required to apply for a certificate of arrears but the Registrar may *suo*

motu issue such a certificate. But it is pertinent to note that the section does not provide for any provision for any opportunity to the debtor to defend the claim against him before issuing of the certificate. The section only requires the Registrar to make such inquiries as he deems fit and there is no provision for appeal to any higher authority or Court, except for the capacity of the High Court under Act 226/227 of the Constitution to intervene.

But for this, the provisions for recovery under the State Co-operative laws are less burdensome and technical for the Co-operative Banks in India.

Further, a careful analysis of the SARFAESI Act, 2002 states that at each and every step of recovery under SARFAESI Act, 2002 man power and capital is required e.g. requirement of officers while taking possession, publication cost of notices in newspapers, etc. As per the provisions of the act these cost and expenses Bank may recover from the defaulter, however in cases where no recovery is forthcoming these expenses become burdensome on the balance sheet of the bank till the time they are fully recovered. Practically, there is likelihood that these expenses may burden the already burdened and financially weak Co-operative banks.

Furthermore, unlike recovery procedures under the State Co-operative laws can be challenged before the Debt Recovery Tribunal which again is very time and money consuming.

2. The applicability of the SARFAESI Act, 2002 would be of no use for Rural Co-operative banks which primarily deal with agricultural credit where the security is mainly agricultural land and security forbidden from attachment under Section 60(1), Code of Civil Procedure, 1908 by virtue of Section 31 of the SARFAESI Act, 2002.

CONCLUSION

The inclusion of the Co-operative banks under the SARFAESI Act, 2002 is indeed a welcome step to strengthen the recovery mechanism of Co-operative banks as it not only confers quasi-judicial power on the Banks but it also facilitates for purchase of NPAs of Co-operative Banks by Asset Reconstruction Companies which is a very effective mechanism of getting rid of the bad loans off the Balance sheet. However, strategic recovery mechanism needs to be implemented for recovery of advances where there is agricultural security as the same is outside the purview of the applicability of SARFAESI Act, 2002.

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- 6) https://rbidocs.rbi.org.in/rdocs/Publications/PDFs/05CHPT5_24122019878A5AF64EB74900B7AD6FF7093EE45F.PDF (Accessed 13 May, 2020 03:43AM)
- 7) <https://indiankanoon.org/doc/156404699/> (Accessed 13 May 2020 02:46 AM)

Judicial Efforts in Managing Groundwater in India: Human Rights Perspective

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Abstract

India is known by its major rivers named Indus, Brahmaputra and Ganga in the north and Mahanadi, Godavari, Krishna and Cauveri in the middle and south India feeding 132.92 crores people exercising their rights freely over these rivers but several reports published recently have shown the depleting situation in terms of water level.

Ground water is an annually replenish-able resource but its availability is non-uniform in space and time. As per the report of Ministry of Water Resources, River Development and Ganga Rejuvenation (MoWR, RD & GR), Contribution of ground water is nearly 62% in irrigation, 85% in rural water supply and 45% in urban water supply. According to Central Groundwater Board's latest report, more than 60 % wells in the country show a decline in the level of groundwater. MoWR, RD & GR, brought out the Draft National Water Framework Bill, 2015 and Groundwater Model Bill, 2016. It provided an overarching national legal framework for the protection, conservation, regulation and management of water as a vital but stressed natural resource, while including the management of river basins. But the draft Bill does not focus on critical aspects of Groundwater Management.

The Researcher, in the present paper, discussed and analyzed the efforts made by legislature in protecting natural resources from pollution and tried to identify the reason for depletion in the groundwater level with the help of various case laws and how it affects the Human Rights of citizens. Further, paper highlighted the policies, latest laws, bye-laws, regulations and notifications governing or managing groundwater.

Keywords: Water, Groundwater, Judiciary, Legislature, Human Rights

INTRODUCTION

The Union Budget as presented by Honorable Finance Minister Smt. Nirmala Sitharaman dated February 01, 2020 had main focus on “liquid and grey water management” along with “waste management”, where, under Prime Minister’s “Nal se jal’ scheme, government proposes rupees 3 lacs sixty crore towards piped water supply to households. “Wellness, Water and Sanitation” were presented as important components of “Aspirational India” which was categorized under the main theme of “Ease of Living”. This shows the kind of significance ‘water’ has gained after alarming data presented by numerous global and Indian private plus governmental research agencies³.

According to the report published with a title “Water Stress Index, 2019”, presented by a London-based risk analytics firm Verisk Maplecroft⁴, among most high-risk countries of the world, India is placed at forty sixth rank. It calculated the water uptake rates of houses, businesses and farming

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³ www.indiabudget.gov.in (Jan. 02, 2020, 10:05 AM).

⁴ <https://www.maplecroft.com/risk-indices/water-stress-index/> (Jan. 03, 2020, 11:00AM).

sectors and the accessible resources in rivers, lakes and streams and planned the index with protruded population evolution tends to rank the cities facing the bear-sized threat to their water resources.

As per Composite Water Management Index study published on June 17, 2018 by National Institution for Transforming India (NITI) Aayog, India reports for just about seventeen percent of the world's population but a mere four percent of worldwide freshwater resources.

The anatomy convey that farming ingest eighty four percent of the overall water obtainable, industry twelve percent and home usage for the rest four percent. Also, the NITI Aayog press notes that we, in India, use two to four times much water to bring forth one unit of major crops, compared to the other principal farming nations like China and the US. We need to increase water usage efficiency.

As far as groundwater management in states is concerned, it has been found that Gujarat, Madhya Pradesh and Andhra Pradesh are managing waters efficaciously and on the other hand, Meghalaya, Uttar Pradesh, Bihar and Nagaland are worst performing states in managing groundwater resources. About eighty five percent of the rural population in India is exclusively dependent on groundwater, which is being exhausted at a high rate⁵. The nontarnishable groundwater potential of the country has been estimated by the Ministry of Water Resources as four hundred thirty one km³ per year. The potential available for irrigation is three hundred sixty km³ per year; the leftover sixteen percent is available for drinking, industrial and other functions. The anatomy for net draft of groundwater considering the existing usage signals that a considerable portion (about sixty eight percent) of the total potential remains unexploited. However, the evolution of groundwater in assorted sphere of the country has not been homogeneous. Extremely extensive evolution of groundwater in definite fields in the nation has effected in over utilization, starring to decrements in the levels of groundwater and insufficiency of drinking water during summer⁶.

Water Aid's State of the World's Water study, 2017, unveils that India, one of the world's quickest flourishing economies and place to seventeen percent of the world's population, has the most number of rural citizenry surviving without admittance to clean water. With sixty seven percent of the country's population living in rural areas and seven percent of the rural population

⁵ S. R. Wate, *An Overview of Policies Impacting Water Quality and Governance in India*, *International Journal of Water Resources Development*, 28:2, 265-279, (2012).

⁶ Rao S, et al. *Signaling at the gate: phosphorylation of the mitochondrial protein import machinery*. *Cell Cycle* 10(13):2083-90 (2011).

even at present living without access to clean water, India's rural poor are extremely vulnerable to the effects of uttermost weather conditions and climate change.

Thus, looking at the preceding facts and figures, the government of several states and union government has possibly taken an effort to control pollution and enhance quality of groundwater management in their respective boundaries. As far as judiciary is concerned, it has, from time to time raised serious concern over groundwater management by the executives and given several directions to improve the situation of water stressed areas.

The report, based on latest data from the ministry of urban development (2013), census 2011 and Central Pollution Control Board, estimates that seventy five to eighty percent of water pollution by volume is from domestic sewerage, while untreated sewerage flowing into water bodies including rivers have almost doubled in recent years. This in turn is leading to increasing burden of vector borne diseases, cholera, dysentery, jaundice and diarrhea etc.

Water pollution is found to be a major cause for poor nutritional standards and development in children also. Of the world's top twenty polluted cities, thirteen are in India compared to just three in China. Air pollution slashes life expectancy by three years for the six hundred sixty million Indians who live in cities, including Delhi. In China, the corresponding dip is marginally lower at three years. The Ganga and Yamuna are ranked among the world's ten most polluted rivers. China has just one. An evaluation in February ranked Vapi in Gujarat and Sukinda in Odisha among the ten most environmentally-degraded zones in the world. China had no entries on the list. Both countries were saddled with almost identical environmental concerns a decade ago, but China cleaned many of its polluted rivers and managed to check the spiraling urban air pollution through stringent rules.

A 2015 survey study published by the Centre for Science and Environment, a Delhi-based NGO, says that the country's overall environmental standards has been declined because of river pollution, which is worse now than it was three decades ago, piling garbage in cities and increasingly toxic urban air. A three-year investigation of the water quality in two hundred ninety rivers by the Central Pollution Control Board said about sixty six percent of the stretches monitored had high organic pollution. It means 8,400 km of these rivers are badly polluted and not fit for supporting aquatic life. "Increasing flow of untreated waste water from cities into these rivers is the reason for our rivers getting polluted.

Water use across various sectors in India is on the rise. Various estimates and projections indicate an increasing trend in water demand for agriculture, industrial and domestic uses in the coming decades. India is also projected to move into the category of water stressed nation by 2020.

The water demand for the industrial sector is on a rise and will account for eight point five and ten point one percent of the total freshwater abstraction in 2025 and 2050 respectively. This is a four percent rise from the current level of six percent of the total freshwater abstraction by the industries in 2010.

The guidelines framed for plan of action and the groundwater regulatory framework comprehend various facets relating to groundwater ownership, environment, observation, conception, grant, power tariff, licensing, enrollment, and people's involvement. The contribution of groundwater for drinking, industrial, and irrigation use has been on the increase during the last two decades. Promiscuous extraction of groundwater already poses the danger of aquifers going arid in some environs of the country.

WATER AS A HUMAN RIGHT

Since the old times, water has been respected as one of the most basic human right which conjures life to all living creatures. Thus, in this way the concept of right to water emerged as fundamental part of nature that became the backbone of yet another right in the form of right to have an adequate living and a quality life⁷.

The right to water has been discovered in various international treaties and customary prescripts. It is in being in both express and implied form. This right can be reasoned out from a number of international conventions which are binding upon all states making it incumbent on all states to respect the rights relating to water.

Apart from the international protection accorded to right of water, there also exist a number of regional instruments strongly advocating the protection and promotion of water rights in their particular region.

The material on water rights in the domain of international law is existing in many books. It has been acknowledged as one of the elementary and fundamental rights in international law through several international instruments in the form of international human rights declarations, conventions etc. The major tool in international force includes the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women⁸ (CEDAW), 1979 and The Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC), 1989. Other treaties implicitly recognize the right, for instance the International Covenant on Economic Social and Cultural Rights, 1966. In terms of political declarations, the

⁷ Prof. Aman Mishra, *Right to Water in India: Changing Perceptions, International Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Studies*, 1-5 (2015).

⁸ Please See. Art.14(2) of CEDAW, 1979.

main resolutions were passed by the UN General Assembly and the UN Human Rights Council resolutions both in 2010.

Water rights remain the quintessential status in international sphere for the successful enjoyment of the right to an adequate standard of living and health⁹.

India has been a party to all the major international human rights treaties¹⁰ which have agreed a human rights' status to the right to water. An analysis of these conventions arguably leads us to the premise that 'right to water' should be treated as a basic, fundamental and human right even if it is not expressly mentioned in the human rights conventions.¹¹

While water has not been explicitly recognized as a self-standing human right in international treaties, international human rights law implies peculiar obligations related to access to safe drinking water. These obligations require States to ensure everyone's access to a sufficient amount of safe drinking water for personal and domestic uses, defined as water for drinking, personal sanitation, washing of clothes, food preparation, and personal and household hygiene. These obligations also require States to progressively ensure access to adequate sanitation, as a fundamental element for human dignity and privacy, but also to defend the quality of drinking-water supplies and resources¹².

Under Indian Constitution, numbers of rights have been enumerated but right to water is not explicitly recognized as a fundamental right. the Right to water has been secured as a basic human appropriate by the Indian Supreme Court as a major aspect of the Right to Life ensured under Article 21 of the Indian constitution. The privilege to life has been extended altogether finished the most recent three decades to incorporate the privilege to well being and the privilege to a perfect situation which can incorporate the privilege to clean drinking water. Constitution of India manages

⁹ In recent years, more explicit articulations of this view supporting the right to water have been made such as resolution of the UNO passed during the United Nations Water Conference in 1977 as under: "All people, whatever their stage of development and their social and economic conditions, have the right to have access to drinking water in quantum and of a quality equal to their basic needs."

¹⁰ For example, India has ratified the following treaties: the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (1979); the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (1979); the Convention on the Rights of Children (1993); the Convention on the Elimination of Discrimination Against Women (1993); the Convention Against Torture and other Inhumane or Degrading Treatment or Punishment (1997); the International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination (1969).

¹¹ Ruchi Pant, "From Communities' Hands to MNCs' BOOTS: A Case Study from India on Right to Water" (Right to Water Project) Submitted to Rights and Humanity, UK October 2003, P5.

¹² United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights "The Right to Water Fact Sheet No. 35," Switzerland. (Jan. 05, 2020, 12:10 PM) <http://www.ohchr.org/Documents/Publications/FactSheet35en.pdf> .

certain principal privileges of human. There is one such right which is the fundamental need of people, yet at the same time it isn't given due significance in our constitution, that is 'Water'¹³.

Notwithstanding article 21, Article 39 (b) of the mandate standards of state arrangement (DPSP), which the Constitution proclaims to be non-justifiable, perceives the guideline of equivalent access to the material assets of the group. Article 39 (b) orders that 'the State should, specifically, coordinate its arrangement towards securing that the proprietorship and control of the material assets of the group are so circulated as best to sub serve the benefit of all.'¹⁴ Further, alternate spaces pertinent for water rights and administration are Parts IX and IXA of the Constitution consolidated by the now acclaimed 73rd and 74th Amendments to the Constitution of India that were brought into impact in 1993.

73rd Amendment of the Constitution had thrown a Constitutional basic on all the state governments to think of a fitting Panchayat Raj Act enumerating meaningful vote based devolution of capacities, functionaries, and assets. In particular, it engages states to enrich panchayats with such powers and expert to empower them to work as foundations of self-government and goes ahead to list 'Drinking Water', 'Water Management', 'Minor Irrigation', and 'Watershed Development' as subjects under the ward of panchayats.¹⁵

In a comparative vein, the 74th Amendment to the Constitution of India perceives nearby self administration as an enforceable perfect and obliges the state governments to constitute urban neighbourhood bodies. 74th Amendment likewise requires that 'the Legislature of a State may, by law, invest the Municipalities with such powers and specialist as might be important to empower them to work as organisations of self-government'¹⁶ 'matters that might be endowed' to the Municipalities incorporate 'Water supply for household, mechanical and business purposes', among others. Both the 73rd and 74th Amendments to the Constitution motivated changes in the current state level panchayats, metropolitan enterprise and municipal board laws in order to align them with the command under the Constitutional Amendments¹⁷.

Groundwater ownership legally stems from the Easement Act of 1882, within which groundwater is treated as real (not movable) property. The states have responsibility to regulate groundwater under "water supplies" within the Entry 17 of List II in the Seventh Schedule. Additionally, based on

¹³ M. Swathi & R. Dhivya, Constitutional Perspective of Right to Water in India, *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, 3909-3919 (2018).

¹⁴ *Ibid.*

¹⁵ <http://savethewater.org/2013/01/06/water-news-article-31-petition-everyone-has-theright-to-clean-and-accessible-water/> (Jan. 06, 2020, 13.00 PM).

¹⁶ <https://instead.com/blog/article-31-the-right-to-clean-and-safe-water> (Jan. 06, 2020, 13.00 PM).

¹⁷ <http://books.openedition.org/irdeditions/4810?lang=en> (Jan. 06, 2020, 13.00 PM).

public trust principles, the Supreme Court has decreed that the central government is responsible to protect water under Article 21 of the Constitution, which asserts that no person shall be deprived of his life or personal liberty except according to procedure established by law¹⁸.

JUDICIAL EFFORTS

Courts have developed the via media techniques to incorporate the essential 'human rights' which are precondition for better 'enjoyment' of other fundamental rights in to the "part of fundamental rights." One such technique developed by the courts is doctrine of emanation. In the 7-judge case of Maneka Gandhi¹⁹ BHAGWATI J., for the majority, observed that —

"even if a fundamental right is not specifically named in Article 19(1), it may still be a fundamental right covered by some clause of that article, "if it is an integral part of a named fundamental right or partakes of same basic nature and character as that fundamental right," that is: "it emanates from a named fundamental right or its existence is necessary in order to make the exercise of a named fundamental right meaningful and effective."²⁰

Therefore applying this theory of emanation, the Supreme Court has evolved the right to water as constitutional right elevated as fundamental right.

In Hamid Khan V. State of M.P and Ors.²¹, The Supreme Court observed that

“Under Article 47 of the Constitution of India, it is the responsibility of the State to raise the level of nutrition and the standard of living of its people and the improvement of public health. It is incumbent on State to improve the health of public providing unpolluted drinking water. State in present case has failed to discharge its primary responsibility. It is also covered by Article 21 of the Constitution of India and it is the right of the citizens of India to have protection of life, to have pollution free air and pure water”.

In Subhash Kumar v. State of Bihar²², Supreme Court held that a right to life includes right to live properly and have the benefit of all natural recourses i.e. unpolluted air and water. It was observed that "Right to live is a fundamental right under Article 21 of the Constitution and it includes the

¹⁸ T. N. Narasimhan, Economic and Political Weekly, Vol. 43, No. 7 (Feb. 16 - 22, 2008), pp. 21-23, 25-27.

¹⁹ Maneka v. Union of India, AIR 1970 SC 597.

²⁰ However, he also observed that “But, it is not enough that a right claimed... flows or emanates from a named fundamental right or that its existence is necessary in order to make the exercise of a named fundamental right meaningful and effective...What is necessary to be seen is, whether the right claimed.. .is an integral part of a named fundamental right or partakes of the same basic nature and character as the named fundamental right so that the exercise of such right is in reality and substance nothing but an instance of the exercise of the named fundamental right”

²¹ AIR 1997 MP 191, 1997 (1) MPLJ 587.

²² AIR 1991 SC 420.

right of enjoyment of pollution free water and air for full enjoyment of life. If anything endangers or impairs that quality of life in derogation of laws, a citizen has right to have resource to Article 32 of the Constitution for removing the pollution of water or Air which may be detrimental to the quality of life."

In *A.P. Pollution Control Board II v Prof. M.V. Naidu and Others*²³, the right to access to clean drinking water is fundamental to life and there is a duty on the state under Article 21 to provide clean drinking water to its citizens. The State is duty bound not only to provide adequate drinking water but also to protect water sources from pollution and encroachment. Any act of the State that allows pollution of a water body must be treated as arbitrary and contrary to public interest and in violation of the right to clean water under Article 21.

In the case of *Puttappa Honnappa Talavar v. Deputy Commissioner, Dharwad*²⁴, it held that the right to life also includes the right to have access to clean drinking.

The *Vellore Citizen's Welfare Forum v. Union of India*²⁵ case dealt with the issue of water pollution by the discharge of toxic effluents from tanneries located in the state of Tamil Nadu. The Supreme Court looked into Articles 21, 47, 48-A and 51-A(g) as well as the basic provisions of the Water (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1974, Air (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1981 and the Environment Protection Act, 1986 to decide on this case. The twin principles of 'Polluter Pays' and 'Precautionary Principle' were looked into by the Court and subsequently introduced as 'law of the land'.

Yet again in *Narmada Bachao Andolan v. Union of India*²⁶ the Supreme Court has derived the right to water as a human right from the right to life. Here the Court says, water is the basic need for the survival of the human beings and is part of right of life and human rights as enshrined in Article 21 of the Constitution of India." Now it is, therefore, clear that the Supreme Court beyond any doubt recognizes the right to water as a human right and a fundamental right.²⁷

In 1990, the Kerala High Court ruling on a groundwater extraction case involving water supply plan for the island of Lakshadweep ruled that government should not extract groundwater impacting the

²³ [1999] 2 SCC 718.

²⁴ AIR 1998 Kar 10.

²⁵ AIR 1996 SC 2715.

²⁶ AIR 2000 SC 375.

²⁷ Taposik Banerjee "Right to Water: Some Theoretical Issues" Contemporary Issues and Ideas in Social Sciences June 2010 available at <http://journal.ciiss.net/index.php/ciiss/article/viewFile/79/76> (Jan. 06, 2020, 13.00 PM).

sources in future that in turn violated the Article 21²⁸. It ruled: "... the administrative agency cannot be permitted to function in such a manner as to make inroads into the fundamental right under Article 21. The right to life is much more than a right to animal existence and its attributes are manifold, as life itself. A prioritizing of human needs and a new value system has been recognized in these areas.

The right to sweet water and the right to free air are attributes of the right to life, for these are the basic elements which sustain life itself.²⁹

In 2004 giving verdict on a PIL on fast depletion of groundwater in Delhi, the apex court ruled that groundwater is a social asset. It further said that people have the right to use air, water and earth interpreting the Article 21³⁰. It even observed that in groundwater use, domestic and irrigation needs must be prioritized.

Apart from expanding the content of the right to life as including the right to water, the court has, in the context of water pollution, mandated the cleaning up of water sources including rivers³¹ the coastline and even tanks and wells. The concern over pollution of groundwater by unregulated discharge of effluents has led the court to issue mandatory directions for clean up by the polluter and restitution of the soil and groundwater.³²

In *M.C. Mehta v. Union of India*,³³ which concerned the pollution of the river Ganga, the Supreme Court reaffirmed the duty of the government, under Article 21, to ensure a better quality of environment and ordered the government to improve its sewage system.

In *M. C. Mehta v. Union of India*, the Supreme Court of India recognized that groundwater is a public asset, and that citizens have the right to the use of air, water, and earth as protected under Article 21 of the Constitution.³⁴

Significantly, the Supreme Court has recognized that water is a community resource to be held by the State in public trust in recognition of its duty to respect the principle of inter-generational equity. In *M.C Mehta v. Kamal Nath*³⁵ the Court declared that: Our legal system - based on English

²⁸ Indira Khurana and Richard Mahapatra Right to Water and Sanitation available at http://re.indiaenvironmentportal.org.in/files/Righttowaterandsanitation_march252009_draft.pdf (Jan. 06, 2020, 13.00 PM).

²⁹ Ruchi Pant "*From Communities' Hands to MNCs' BOOTS: A Case Study from India on Right to Water*" (*Right to Water Project*) Submitted to Rights and Humanity, UK October 2003, P5

³⁰ *MC Mehta V. Union of India* 2004(12) SCC 118.

³¹ *M.C. Mehta v. Union of India*, (1998) 2 S.C.R. 530.

³² *Hinch Lal Tiwari v. Kamala Devi* AIR 2001 SC 3215.

³³ (1998) 2 S.C.R. 530.

³⁴ *Ibid.*

³⁵ (1997) 1 S.C.C. 388.

common law – includes the public trust doctrine as part of its jurisprudence. The State is the trustee of all natural resources which are by nature meant for public use and enjoyment. Public at large is the beneficiary of the seashore, running waters, airs, forests and ecologically fragile lands. The State as a trustee is under a legal duty to protect the natural resources. These resources meant for public use cannot be converted into private ownership.

In *Indian Council of Enviro-Legal Action vs. Union of India*³⁶ (the Bichhri pollution case), following the decision in the Oleum Gas leak case and based on the polluter pays principle, the polluting industries were directed to compensate for the harm caused by them to the villagers in the affected areas, specially to the soil and to the underground water.

In *Shanti Star Builders vs. Narayan Totame*³⁷ the Supreme Court held that right to life is guaranteed in a civilised society would take within its sweep the right to food, the right to clothing, the right to decent environment and a reasonable accommodation to live in.

In a recent case of *Sunita Pandey v. Union of India*³⁸, the bench stated that the existing plan of action needs to be re-looked as it has quite relaxed time lines and the strategies needs to redrawn by a suitable mechanism because of urgency in the matter. This needs to be monitored by Central Government on war footing to enforce Fundamental Right to access potable drinking water which is part of ‘Right to Life’ under the Constitution of India.

In another case decided on 22-10-2018³⁹, the prime consideration was whether the basic amenities of water and electricity shall be granted to the petitioner or not. It was stated that as they were an integral part of Right to Life within the meaning of Article 21 of the Constitution of India calls for immediate action. Thus till the title dispute remains pending, for that considerable period the petitioner shall be granted the same on subject to their payment of requisite charges and shall remain purely an interim and adhoc measure till the title dispute was decided.

The above judgments are illustrative judgments of how judicially the right to water has been dealt with. However, it makes a difference, when one sits to read the judicial pronouncements as source of law in contrast to comprehensive legislative policy. Though judicial decisions have at times acted as grounds for prompting the executive reactions yet, they such pronouncement cannot partake the character of legislative wordings. Hence, right to water which is judicially upheld needs to be judiciously addressed by legislative enactment and comprehensive executive policies⁴⁰.

³⁶ 1996 3 SCC 212.

³⁷ 1990(1)SCC 520.

³⁸ 2019 SCC OnLine NGT 277.

³⁹ *Madan Lal v. State of Himachal Pradesh*, 2018 SCC OnLine HP 1495.

⁴⁰ Views are personal.

Part of the reason for not acknowledging the right to water as an independent right is that once such an explicit acknowledgement is there, it puts a greater responsibility on states to actualize the right. The accountability is increased. This is precisely why struggles and movements all over the world are strongly advocating the explicit declaration of water as a fundamental right⁴¹.

The courts, in nearly every case where it is shown that water is used in an unreasonable manner or diverted from its natural source to the damage of mill owners, have promptly awarded damages for the same and even the state has no legal right to grant the privilege of taking water from such lakes as are under state control, without the consent of the riparian owners of the land situated upon the outlets thereof.

CONCLUSION

It is to conclude that the question of groundwater governance in India is twofold. First, we need to substantially support and empower the community based systems of decision-making. Second, the existing legal framework and groundwater management institutions have to be fundamentally re-engineered to play a role facilitating and enabling community action.

Thus, there is a need to introduce a number of supply and demand management strategies to tackle the exploitation of groundwater. Finally, to ensure equitable access to water, water entitlement reforms and water delivery norms must consider conjunctive use of surface-water and groundwater resources.

An integrated, holistic approach is needed for the management and protection of water. What is more required is that the groundwater-monitoring networks has to be upgraded and improved. The chemical and quantitative status of groundwater bodies has to be determined, providing a measure of the current situation and a signpost to future requirements.

⁴¹ Shripad Dharmadhikary *Recognising the human right to water* 17 (2010).

Regulations of Real Estate Sector in India: Legal issues and Challenges

Pradeep Kumar Singh*

“Real estate is an imperishable asset, ever increasing in value. It is the most solid security that human ingenuity has devised. It is the basis of all security and about the only indestructible security.” - Russell Sage

ABSTRACT:

Real estate sector plays a catalytic role in fulfilling the needs and demand for housing and infrastructure in the country and is an important pillar of the economy. While this sector has grown significantly in recent years, it has been largely unregulated, with absence of professionalism and lack of adequate consumer protection. It had no regulator like there are for other specific sectors like insurance (IRDAI), telecom (TRAI), stock markets (SEBI) etc. There were so many shots and illegal activities in Real Estate sector. Unregulated developers would often make empty promises about the date of completion, requisite charges, carpet area etc. to defraud buyers and extract huge amounts of money from them. Thus, investment in the real estate sector used to be a risky one.

Therefore, The Real Estate (Regulation and Development) Act, 2016 (hereafter referred as RERA) was enacted with various checks and restrictions placed on builders of project apart from transparency in transaction to convince buyers that the money they invest in a project will not be fraudulently siphoned off and that they will be reimbursed for any unjustified delay. However, The Real Estate (Regulation and Development) Act, 2016 is not untouched with loopholes. In this context the present paper discusses and examines various enactments regulating real estate sector and pragmatic approach of RERA.

KEY WORDS: Real Estate, RERA, Force Majeure, Escrow Account, Carpet Area, Promoter.

I. INTRODUCTION:

In India, real estate industry ranks second in the world in terms of generating employment for the people of India and contributing to the Gross Domestic Product of the country. The Union Budget 2019-2020 has paved an optimistic way ahead for the affordable housing sector by introducing additional tax benefits for the first time homebuyers which will enhance the housing supply in very

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rapid manner. The real estate sector in India is expected to reach a market size of 1 trillion US dollar by 2030.

Currently, more and more researches are being conducted in relation to the promotion of the sustainable development in several areas to alleviate the relevant problem. Since 'sustainability' and 'sustainable development' encompasses economic security and growth, environmental quality and integrity, social cohesion and quality of life, empowerment and governance, hence, the role of the real estate sector in the promotion of the sustainable development become predominant because it involves one of the basic pursuit of life, viz. roti, kapda and makan and thus has major impact on the state of socio-economic status. Since Real estate is inseparable from human economy in its social form, and all plans of social reform must be directed toward an appropriate distribution of economic goods including housing and infrastructure. During the inflation period, back in 2010, the real estate industry faced a major setback, as many projects stopped when the builders declared themselves bankrupt, and people lost their money. The home buyers had a complaint that the real estate laws were in favour of the builders and builders used to exploit them. The earlier framework and regulatory regime was inadequate to address all the concerns of buyers and developers in the real estate sector. Consumer grievances were addressed largely by the consumer forums under the Consumer Protection Act, 1986 (COPRA) and claims of unfair trade practice by the Competition Commission of India (CCI) under the Competition Act, 2002 (CA). Different forums at different points of time addressed issues such as unfair buyer's agreement, breach of contract, and illegal construction. The need of a single regulator leading to dispute resolution in the real estate sector was pointed out by the CCI.

In view of the above, Parliament enacted the Real Estate (Regulation and Development) Act, 2016 which aims at protecting the rights and interests of consumers and promotion of uniformity and standardization of business practices and transactions in the real estate sector. It attempts to balance the interests of consumers and promoters by imposing certain responsibilities on both. It seeks to establish symmetry of information between the promoter and purchaser, transparency of contractual conditions, set minimum standards of accountability and a fast-track dispute resolution mechanism. This Act has been introduced by the Union Government but the regulations are in the hands of the State Government. It prescribed that the states must not dilute the provisions and the spirit of the central Act. Now, the buyers who feel cheated on or harassed by the builder, they can approach to the RERA authority. RERA is giving the Indian Real Estate industry its first regulator.

II. MEANING OF THE TERM "REAL ESTATE":

The term 'real estate' refers to land as well as building. The word 'land' includes-- the air above and the ground below and any buildings or structures on it. The construction of commercial houses, residential housing, and business spaces, such as hotels, restaurants, theaters, and industrial buildings, namely factories and government buildings, are all covered by the real estate sector. Thus the term real estate connotes immovable property which can be either land or building or both.

The real estate transaction includes:-

- a. Purchase,
- b. Sale and
- c. Development of land (both residential and non-residential buildings).

Real estate is a term that encompasses land along with those improvements to it such as commercial and residential structures, roadways and ports that are all fixed in location.

III. COMPREHENSIVE VIEW OF MAJOR INDIAN LAWS RELATED TO REAL ESTATE SECTOR:

Real estate in India is governed and impacted by combination of Federal and State- specific laws. This is largely because, in accordance with Article 246 of The Constitution of India, 'Land' is the subject matter of State List of the seventh schedule to the Constitution of India for which state has exclusive right to legislate. While Transfer of Property other than agricultural land, registration of deeds and documents and Contracts other than for agricultural lands fall under the concurrent list of seventh schedule of The Constitution of India which are subject for which state as well as center both can make law. The Laws applicable to Real Estate business can be divided in five groups:

- i. Land- Related Laws
- ii. Environment Laws
- iii. Construction Laws
- iv. Registration Laws
- v. Labour Laws

Land Related Laws:

Since 'land' is the subject matter of state list so state has exclusive right to make laws on the land and land related issues such as 'Transfer of right and interest in immovable property, or Acquisition of land for public purpose' by Government.

Environment Laws:

Environment laws are to protect the environment from pollution due to development & construction activities and to restrict construction in prohibited areas. Environment laws are applicable as:

- Environment Protection Act 1986.

- Water (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1974.
- The Air (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1981.

Construction Laws:

Construction laws ensure planned development and safe buildings fit for human habitations by providing:-

- Master Plan
- Zonal Plan
- Building Plan
- Fire Safety
- Electricity
- Water Supply
- Sewage/ Drainage

Registration Laws:

Registration laws are to protect the interest of the parties to an instrument by providing evidential value to the instrument of any nature. The purpose of the Act is the conservation of evidence, assurances, title, and publication of documents and prevention of fraud.

Following registration laws are applicable:

- Registration Act, 1908 (For registration of compulsorily registerable document)
- Indian Stamp Act, 1899 (Stamp duty to be paid on registration)

Labour Laws:

Labour laws are for the welfare of the workers / labours. Following labour laws are applicable to real estate:

- Building and Other Construction Workers' (Regulation of employment and conditions of service) Act, 1996 & Rules OF 1998 (workers safety, health & Welfare measures including necessary amenities)
- Building and Other Construction Workers' Welfare Cess Act,1996 (Cess Payment on cost of construction for workers welfare)

Apart from the above, there are some key legislations governing real estate in India:

Transfer of Property Act, 1882:

The Transfer of Property Act governs the transfer of property by various means. Sales, mortgages (other than by way of deposit of title deeds) and exchanges of immovable property are required to

be registered by virtue of The Transfer of Property Act, 1882. Property can be transferred in either ways:

1. Sale
2. Mortgage
3. Lease
4. Exchange
5. Gift

Indian Easement Act, 1882:

This Act governs the law relating to easement rights to immovable property.

Indian Contract Act, 1872:

This legislation specifies when a party can be said to have the capacity to contract. All the requirements of a valid contract, i.e. consideration, intention to contract and validity under the law of the land must be satisfied.

Land Revenue Codes:

Various states in India have formulated their own land revenue codes, which govern laws relating to agricultural land- holding, land revenue, kinds of tenancy and matters connected thereto. The said codes encapsulate division and classes of immovable property in a state, restrictions on transfer thereto, power and duties of revenue officers, rules, regulations and penalties for contravening such codes.

Foreign Exchange Management Act, 1999 (FEMA) and Foreign Direct Investment Policy (FDI Policy):

FEMA and regulations pursuant thereto govern the purchase / sale of immovable property in India by foreign entities. The consolidated FDI policy governs permissibility of foreign investment in real sector in India along with compliance parameter and exit of such investors. Such foreign investment is regulated by the Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion (DIPP), The Foreign Investment Promotion Board (FIPB) and the Reserve Bank of India (RBI).

Right to Fair Compensation and Transparency in Land Acquisition, Rehabilitation and Resettlement Act, 2013:

This Act governs the acquisition of private lands by government for certain public purposes or for a company and the compensation and rehabilitative measures to be undertaken thereto by the government.

The Real Estate (Regulation and Development) Act, 2016 (RERA):

This Act governs development, marketing and sale of real estate projects to protect the interest of consumers in the real estate sector. The Act established an adjudicating mechanism for speedy dispute redressal (The Real Estate Regulatory Authority and Appellate Tribunal) and mandates compulsory registration of projects and key players in real estate. Corresponding RERA rules and regulations have been adopted by states to ensure effective implementation of the central Act.

In addition to the above, the real estate sector in India is also governed by various State / Local / Municipal laws, policies and customs, including nuances in respect of urban development, slum rehabilitation / improvement, rent control, apartment ownership, Building Codes / By-laws, property tax, Special Economic Zones (SEZs), benami transactions, environmental protection, land pooling policies, land ceiling, land use and zoning norms, real estate investment trust regulations, dispute resolution legislations such as The Consumer Protection Act ,1986, The Arbitration and Conciliation Act, 1996, etc.

IV. ROAD TOWARDS REFORM AGAINST ANOMALIES IN REAL ESTATE LAWS:

An individual pines for his own house and to turn his dream in to reality he spends his lifetime earnings and savings. Majority of home buyers are aggrieved by the delay confronted in timely delivery of projects. This inexplicable delay in delivery of housing projects cripples the sole purpose of investing in real estate and converts an asset into liability. Buyer-seller agreements in Indian real estate sector have been subject of a number of cases at Competition Commission of India (CCI) and National Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission (NCDRC) during the last ten years.

While a large number of cases, involving heavy-handedness of real estate players, have been brought to the CCI, majority of them had to be rejected by the CCI on account of absence of dominant position on the part of company concerned. However, the CCI order on *Belaire Owners' Association v. DLF Limited, HUDA & Ors.*¹ and the orders by Competition Appellate Tribunal (COMPAT) later on sparked country wide debate on fair treatment to consumers in this industry and also that policy and regulatory framework needs to be tweaked to protect home buyers.

In this case, the CCI (Competition Commission of India) extensively dealt with the issue of abuse of dominant position and one-sided development agreements. DLF was held liable for abuse of dominant position under the Competition Act, 2002 and was slapped with a penalty of

¹ Case No. 19/2010

Rs. 630 crores. The CCI also directed DLF to modify conditions imposed on its buyers. However, in appeal COMPAT (Competition Appellate Tribunal) stayed CCI's order regarding modification of the terms of agreement but barred DLF from implementation of the impugned agreement.

Vishal Arya v. Unitech Limited² In this case, the Complainant was aggrieved by the inordinate delay caused in completion and possession of his flat booked with Unitech. The Complainant had deposited the entire amount of flat with Unitech and according to the agreement the possession of flat was assured by March, 2009. However, the construction of flat had not yet even started. Aggrieved by this, the Complainant prayed either for immediate delivery of flat or refund of the entire amount along with interest and litigation charges. In reply, Unitech contended that the delay was caused by *force majeure*³ circumstances which was beyond its control.

In such case, Commission was of the view that there was a sheer deficiency in the services of Unitech and they were only enjoying the fruits of deposited amount and on account of mental agony suffered by the buyers, the Commission directed Unitech to refund the entire amount along with interest @10% p.a. and also to pay Rs. 2.50 lac as compensation to the Complainant for mental agony.

Suman Nandi & Anr. Vs. Unitech Limited & Anr.⁴ In this case, the builder took the defence of shortage of labour etc. due to common wealth games in 2010 for delay in delivery of project. The NCDRC while rejecting the builder's response observed that the plea was not acceptable for the reason that buyer's agreement were of the year 2006 to 2010 and if the opposite parties intended to comply with the terms of agreement, they would have raised substantial construction before common wealth games. NCRDC further remarked that till date, the possession of the apartments had not been handed over to the complainants which clearly indicated the deliberate delay and negligence on the part of the builder and the builder could not be permitted to hide behind a bogus plea of force majeure or exceptions provided in clause 9(b) of the Buyer's Agreement.

Home buyers had been complaining that real estate transactions were uneven and heavily in bias towards the developers. There were many more ways in which buyers were deprived of their rights such as-

1. The buyers had no right to information.

² Complaint No. 9/322

³ **Force majeure:** Force majeure refers to any event or combination of events which materially and adversely affect the performance of obligations of either party to a contract and is not within the reasonable control of the affected party.

⁴ CC No.277/2013

2. They had no right to claim for compensation when they did not get the property as per the agreement.
3. The buyers did not had right to ask for the documents of the property.
4. The buyers had no right to ask for refund from the builder in any case.

Plethora of cases involving malpractices by builders goaded our parliamentarians to enact regulatory framework and policy to protect the rights and wealth of consumers. Therefore, Real Estate (Regulation and Development) Act, 2016 was enacted to bring about effective remedies for home buyers and to protect their rights, holding defaulting developers and builders liable for their actions.

V. THE REAL ESTATE (REGULATION AND DEVELOPMENT) ACT, 2016:

The Real Estate (Regulation and Development) Act, 2016 is an Act of the Parliament of India which seeks to protect home-buyers as well as help boost investments in the real estate industry. The Act establishes a Real Estate Regulatory Authority (RERA) in each state for regulation of the real estate sector and also acts as an adjudicating body for speedy dispute resolution. The bill was passed by the Rajya sabha on 10 March 2016 and by the Lok sabha on 15 March 2016. The Act came into force on 1 May 2016 with 59 of 92 sections notified. Remaining provisions came into force on 1 May 2017. Under the Act, the central and state governments, are required to notify their own rules under the Act on the basis of the model rules framed under the central Act. RERA is a central legislation though land is a state subject on which only the state government is empowered to frame laws. Hence, RERA being a central legislation, is adopted by each state government in India in its respective state assembly and has also framed its respective rules and regulations to implement RERA in its territory. In India, RERA has been enacted and implemented in 26 states as well as Union Territories and in November 2019, it was confirmed by the six north eastern states Nagaland, Arunachal Pradesh, Meghalaya, Manipur, Mizoram, and Sikkim have finally agreed to implement RERA. West Bengal has notified its own real estate law — The Housing and Industrial Regulation Act, 2017 (HIRA) instead of RERA.

Objectives of the Act:

RERA Act is to establish the Real Estate Regulatory Authority for regulation and promotion of the real estate sector and to ensure sale of plot, apartment of building, as the case may be, or sale of real estate project, in an efficient and transparent manner and to protect the interest of consumers in the real estate sector and to establish a monitory mechanism for speedy dispute redressal and also to establish the Appellate Tribunal to hear appeals from the decisions, directions or orders of the Real

Estate Regulatory Authority and the adjudicating officer and for matters connected therewith or incidental thereto.

Procedure of Registration and Penalty on Default:

The Real Estate Act makes it mandatory for all commercial and residential real estate projects where the land is over 500 square metre, or eight apartments, to register with the Real Estate Regulatory (RERA) for launching a project in order to provide greater transparency in project-marketing and execution. Application for registration must be either approved or rejected within a period of 30 days from the date of application by the RERA. On successful registration, the promoter of the project will be provided with a registration number, a login id, and password for the applicants to fill up essential details on the website of the RERA.⁵ The registration granted may be extended by the Authority on an application made by the promoter due to *force majeure*.⁶ Real estate agents who facilitate selling or purchase of properties must take prior registration.⁷ Such agents will be issued a single registration number for each State or Union Territory, which must be quoted by the agent in every sale facilitated by him.

The RERA Act gives specific penalties for offences by promoters, real estate agents, builders and other parties who are involved under the ambit of this act:-

- For non-registration of the project with the RERA Authority: 10% of the total estimated cost of the project.
- Where a project has not been registered and any order or direction for the same has been issued by the authorities: Up to 3 years of imprisonment with or without fine of 10% of the estimated cost of the project.
- Where information or advertisement regarding the project is found to be false: 5% of the estimated cost of the project.
- Where an order of the RERA has been contravened or has not been executed: Daily penalty for every day after passing of the order which has been contravened upto 5% of the estimated cost of the project.
- Where an order of the Appellate Tribunal has been contravened: Upto 3 years imprisonment with or without fine of upto 5% of the estimated cost of the project.

Protection of buyers :

⁵ Vide Ss. 3,4,5 of RERA2016.

⁶ Section 6 RERA 2016 explanation: The expression "force majeure" shall mean a case of war, flood, drought, fire, cyclone, earthquake or any other calamity caused by nature affecting the regular development of the real estate project.

⁷ Vide Ss.59,60,61,64 of RERA 2016

The Act prohibits unaccounted money from being pumped into the sector and as of now 70 per cent of the money has to be deposited in bank accounts through cheque is now compulsory (Escrow Account).⁸ A major benefit for consumers included in the Act is that builders will have to quote prices based on carpet area not super built-up area, while carpet area has been clearly defined in the Act to include usable spaces like kitchen and toilets.⁹ Net usable floor area is the same as in National Building Code, 2005. Under RERA it is mandatory for the builders to disclose the carpet area. There are many other rights provided to buyers under RERA:

- **False promises**– If there is any contradiction in the promises made by the builder and the property delivered, then the buyer has the right to step away from the project along with compensation.
- **Defect after possession**– Any structural defect in the construction revealed within 5 years after the possession of the building will be repaired by the builder within a maximum of 30 days without cost and the buyer has the right to ask for compensation for the same. The amount of rectification has to be paid by the builder.
- **Delay in possession**– If the builder fails to complete the project on the due date of completion then the buyer has the right to withdraw from the project with the full refund from the buyer along with the compensation. The buyers also have an option to continue with the project where he is entitled to the compensation of the delay in handing over the project.
- **Defect in the title**– In such a case, the buyer can claim compensation from the builder. The concept of a defect in the title is not barred by limitation.

From time to time several questions were confronted by authorities with regard to remedies and jurisdiction bestowed by RERA and its confliction with other laws.

⁸Vide Section 4(2)(1)(D) RERA 2016.

⁹Section 2 (k) RERA 2016: "carpet area" means the net usable floor area of an apartment, excluding the area covered by the external walls, areas under services shafts, exclusive balcony or verandah area and exclusive open terrace area, but includes the area covered by the internal partition walls of the apartment.

Explanation.— For the purpose of this clause, the expression "exclusive balcony or verandah area" means the area of the balcony or verandah, as the case may be, which is appurtenant to the net usable floor area of an apartment, meant for the exclusive use of the allottee; and "exclusive open terrace area" means the area of open terrace which is appurtenant to the net usable floor area of an apartment, meant for the exclusive use of the allottee;

In the petition titled *M/s M3M India Pvt. Ltd. & Anr. v. Dr. Dinesh Sharma & Anr.*¹⁰ Delhi High Court reiterated that remedies available to home buyers under the Consumer Protection Act, 1986 (CPA) and Real Estate (Development and Regulation) Act, 2016 (RERA) are concurrent.

In *Ajay Nagpal v. Today Homes and Infrastructure Pvt. Ltd.*¹¹ The National Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission (NCDRC) has held that Real Estate (Regulation and Development) Act 2016(RERA) does not bar filing of a complaint under the Consumer Protection Act 1986 against a builder/developer. Section 79 of RERA only prohibits the jurisdiction of Civil Court from entertaining any suit or proceeding in respect of any matter which can be decided by the Authorities constituted under the RERA. As the Consumer Forum are not Civil Courts, the provisions of Section 79 which bars the jurisdiction of Civil Courts, will not be attracted.

In *Kuldeep Kaur V. MVL Ltd.*¹² The Rajasthan Real Estate Regulatory Authority has held that winding up order under Section 279 of the Companies Act 2013 will not bar proceedings under Real Estate (Regulation and Development) Act 2016. The provisions of Section 31 of RERA will prevail over Section 279 of the Companies Act.

Real Estate Regulatory Authority and Appellate Tribunal:

It will help to establish state-level Real Estate Regulatory Authorities (RERAs) to regulate transactions related to both residential and commercial projects and ensure their timely completion and handover. Appellate Tribunals will now be required to adjudicate cases in 60 days as against the earlier provision of 90 days and Regulatory Authorities to dispose of complaints in 60 days while no time-frame was indicated in earlier Bill.

VI. CONSTITUTIONAL VALIDITY OF THE REAL ESTATE (REGULATION AND DEVELOPMENT) ACT 2016:

The provisions of RERA are in addition to the requirement under other laws and Section 89 specifically gives it an overriding effect in case of any inconsistency. The real estate projects are currently regulated by state governments under their respective state town and country planning or apartment ownership legislations and RERA provisions have been in force since May 1, 2017. The RERA, even in its form of a Bill (prior to being passed by Parliament) was an eagerly awaited and hotly contested legislation. Some believe that this Act was legislative overreach by the centre in the

¹⁰ Delhi H.C. 6/9/2019

¹¹ Consumer Case no. 1764/2017 NCDRC

¹² Complaint No. C2018-2127 Raj RERA 09/05/2019

states' domain. While addressing this issue, it is important to note, that, Entry 18 of List II of the Seventh Schedule of the Constitution of India gives the states the right to legislate over inter alia, land, rights in or over land. The RERA however, has been enacted by the Centre by the power vested in it by virtue of Entries 6 and 7 in List III (Concurrent List) of the Seventh Schedule of the Constitution dealing with contracts and the transfer of property. Both Central government and state governments can legislate on matters under the concurrent list. Article 254 of the Constitution specifically provides that central laws will prevail over state laws on matter in the concurrent list. Article 254 (2) of the Constitution mentions that state laws under the concurrent list which have received Presidential assent shall prevail in the state; however, the proviso to this Article gives plenary powers to the Centre to amend, vary or repeal the particular state law. Accordingly, RERA has an over-riding effect on conflicting state laws.

In Real Gem Buildtech Private V. Union of India ¹³

Several builders had challenged the legal validity of the act and its various provisions. They filed cases in High Courts of Bombay, Nagpur, Aurangabad, Bangalore, Jabalpur to challenge The Real Estate (Regulation & Development) Act, 2016.

The government of India had filed a Transfer Petition in the Supreme Court seeking directive that all similar cases in various courts be clubbed and heard by the apex court. The Supreme Court then directed High Court of Bombay to hear the cases filed in Maharashtra with a directive to give a judgment within 2 months. In the meantime, the Supreme Court had stayed all proceedings in other High Courts until this judgment is pronounced. A bench of Justices Naresh Patil and RG Ketkar observed, “ The challenge to constitutional validity of first proviso to section 3(1), 3(2)(a), explanation to section 3, section 4(2) (l) (c), section 4(2) l) (d), section 5(3) and the first proviso to section 6, sections 7,8,18,22,38,40,59,60,61,63,,64 of Real Estate (Regulation & Development) Act, 2016 fails. These provisos are held to be constitutional, valid and legal.”

VII. CHALLENGES IN IMPLEMENTATION OF THE RERA 2016:

The Act is a positive step towards regulating the real estate industry which provides for constitution of a separate authority, regulating the promoters of real estate project as well as the real estate

¹³ Bom. H.C. 6/12/2017 See also: *D. B. Realty Limited and Anr v. The Union Of India* Bom. H.C. 2017, *Mudassar Builders and Developers V. The Union of India* ,Bom. H.C. 2017, *Swapnil Promoters and Developers V. The Union of India* Bom H.C.2017

agents etc., though the Act has not addressed certain issues such as check on environmental damages or approval of the projects having bearing on unforeseen problems arising out of natural calamities such as flood, cyclone which affects the entire city. The rules and regulations passed in the Act are not applicable for the ongoing projects or projects that are held up due to some clearance issues. The scope of the Act is restricted to 'purchase and sale' of real estate projects and it fails to address the approval bottlenecks which continue to haunt builders. The Act has failed to address the issue of obtaining approvals from multiple authorities and introduction of a 'single window clearance' mechanism which is the fundamental requirement in timely completion of projects. Approvals required in a typical real estate project are approval from Tehsildar, Development Authority, Registration Department, State Pollution Control Board, Forest Department, and Coastal Zone Management Authority for obtaining license for a project. The approval of ASI, NHAI, PWD, Civil Aviation department, Fire Department, and Municipal Authorities are required for approval of building plan and clearance before start of work. These authorities will have to streamline their internal processes to meet the expectation of the promoters.

VIII. CONCLUDING REMARKS:

Before the commencement of RERA, there were no bindings and compulsions on the real estate developers and construction pioneers to deliver the property to its respective buyer on time. An inconsiderable delay was usually witnessed which had a negative effect on the financial health of the homebuyer. The legislative regime was not strong enough to curb the developer and the builder guilty of misconduct and also for breaching the terms and conditions of the builder buyer agreement. With the advent of RERA, there began a norm for strict compliances that has to be adhered by each and every developer, builder and construction giant in different parts of the country. Most of the states have established their own RERA offices where they work under the established rules and regulations. The enactment of RERA brought transparency, legality in the contracts and agreements between buyers and sellers. The Act also introduced liabilities of the buyers due to which the buyers are also duty bound to the sellers. The Act has provided a check and balance between the allottees and promoters to have a fair play. Buyers delaying payments and builders delaying hand-over of properties did not share same penalties so far. Now, they will be made equal. The structural defect guarantee shall provide a sense of security on the quality of building to the allottees.

However, it is still too early to say how effectively RERA will be implemented. State Governments have complied with the requirements of creating regulatory bodies charged with registration, dispute settlement, redressal procedure, etc. Home buyers have regained some amount

of confidence in the Real Estate industry. Over the course of the last three years, RERA has come up and grown as an effective weapon for consumers in the real estate sector. However, there remains uncertainty in the implementation of the same. Loopholes are bound to eventually emerge and as they emerge, the fate of the real estate sector will lie in the hands of the regulatory bodies. As of now, RERA has established itself and gained the awareness necessary to protect home buyers.

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An Overview of the Criminal Justice System in India

Dr Shashikant Tripathi*

India is a Union of States and is governed by a written Constitution which came into force on 26 November 1949.¹ India consists of 28 States and 8 Union Territories. Due to its colonial heritage, India follows the Anglo-Saxon Common law justice system. Article 246² of the Constitution provides for three lists which are enumerated in 7th Schedule of the Constitution. List-1 is the Union List³ which enumerates the subjects on which the Parliament of India has exclusive power to make the laws. List2 is the State List⁴ which enumerates the subjects on which the legislature of a state has the power to make laws. The third list is the Concurrent List⁵ which enumerates subjects on

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¹For Indian Constitution see generally, Dr. M.C. Jain, *The Constitution of India*, Vol.I, (India Law House, New Delhi, 6th ed., 2004; H.M. Seervai, *Constitutional Law of India*(N.M. Tripathi Pvt. Ltd. Bombay, 3rdedn. 1988).

²(1) Notwithstanding anything in clauses (2) and (3), Parliament has exclusive power to make laws with respect to any of the matters enumerated in List I in the Seventh Schedule (in this Constitution referred to as the "Union List").

(2) Notwithstanding anything in clause (3), Parliament, and, subject to clause (1), the Legislature of any State also, have power to make laws with respect to any of the matters enumerated in List III in the Seventh Schedule (in this Constitution referred to as the "Concurrent List").

(3) Subject to clauses (1) and (2), the Legislature of any State has exclusive power to make laws for such State or any part thereof with respect to any of the matters enumerated in List II in the Seventh Schedule (in this Constitution referred to as the "State List").

(4) Parliament has power to make laws with respect to any matter for any part of the territory of India not included [in a State] notwithstanding that such matter is a matter enumerated in the State List.

³Some of the items provided under the list are: Defense of India and every part thereof including preparation for defense and all such acts as may be conducive in times of war to its prosecution and after its termination to effective demobilization; Naval, Military and Air Force Works; Central Bureau of Intelligence and Investigation; Prevention detention for reasons connected with Defense, Foreign Affairs, or the security of India, persons subjected to such detention, etc.

⁴Similarly some of the items provided under the list are:Prisons, Reformatories, Bostal Institutions and other institutions of a like nature, and person, detained therein, arrangements with other States for the use of prisons and other institutions; Police (including railway and village police) subject to the provisions of entry 2-A of Union List; Public Order (but not including [the use of any naval, military or air force or any other armed force of the Union or of any other force subject to the control of the Union or of any contingent or unit thereof] in aid of the civil power), etc.

⁵Similarly Concurrent List have also items these are:Criminal law, including all matters included in the I.P.C.at the commencement of this constitution but excluding offences against laws with respect to any of the matters specified in List I or List II and excluding the use of naval, military or air forces or any other armed force of the Union in aid of the civil power; criminal Procedure , including all matters included in the Cr.P.C. at the commencement of this Constitution; Preventive detention for reasons connected with the security of a Stage, the maintenance of Public order, or the maintenance of supplies and services essential to the community, persons subjected to such detention, etc. For details on this aspect see generally: H.K. Saharay,

which both the Indian Parliament and the Legislatures of the State can enact laws, but if there is any conflict or inconsistency between the laws made by the Indian Parliament and the legislature of any state, the law enacted by the Union Parliament will have overriding effect.⁶ Importantly, the “Public Order”⁷ and the “Police”⁸ are enumerated in Entries 1 and 2 respectively of the State List,⁹ meaning thereby, all matters relating to the organisation, structure and regulation of the police force fall within the ambit of the States. However, the ‘Criminal Laws’ and the ‘Criminal Procedure’ are enumerated in List-3, i.e., the Concurrent List. Therefore, both the Indian Parliament and State legislatures have the powers to make substantive and procedural laws in criminal matters.¹⁰ The States can also enact laws on local and special subjects in order to maintain public order and decency. Thus, under the constitutional scheme, the basic criminal laws, viz., the I.P.C., 1860,¹¹ the Cr.P.C., 1973¹² and the I.E.A., 1872¹³ have been enacted by the Indian Parliament.

The Constitution of India: An Analytical Approach (Eastern Law House, Kolkata, 3rd edn., 2002); Dr. L.M. Singhvi, *Constitution of India* (Modern Law Publisher, New Delhi, 2nd edn. Vol. 1, 2007); D.D. Basu, *Commentary on the Constitution of India* (Wadhwa and Company, New Delhi, 8th edn., Vol. 1, 2007).

⁶M.P.Jain, *The Indian Constitutional Law* 614 (Kamal Law House, Calcutta, 5th ed., 1998.). For detail on this topic see generally: P.M. Bakshi, *The Constitution of India* (Madras Law Journal Office, Madras, Vol. IV, 1999); Dr. M.C. Jain, *The Constitution of India* (Indian Law House, New Delhi, 6th edn., Vol.1, 2004); Virender Grover, *The Constitution of India* (Deep and Deep Publications, New Delhi, Vol. II, 1999); H.M. Seervai, *Constitutional Law of India* (N.M. Tripathi Pvt. Ltd., Bombay, 3rd edn., 1988). For cases on this concept see generally; *Prafulla Kumar v. Bank of Khulna*, AIR 1947, Privy Council 60; *Calcutta Gas Company v. State of West Bengal*, AIR 1962 SC 1044; *State of Bombay v. Balsara* AIR 1951 SC 318; *R.S. Joshi v. Ajit Mills*, AIR 1977 SC 2279; *Union of India v. M.S. Dhillon*, AIR 1972 SC 1061; *International Tourism v. State of Haryana*, AIR 1981 SC 774.

⁷ Public order means: In a democratic polity, which is founded on the bedrock of rule of law, maintenance of peace and order assumes paramount importance. Public order is synonymous with peace, safety and tranquillity of the community. Maintenance of public order is a core function of governance. The Indian Constitution, while according a pre-eminent position for the fundamental rights of citizens, recognizes the importance of public order, by providing for legislation imposing reasonable restrictions in the interest of public order. Under the Constitution of India, the Union and the federating units, that is, the States have well-defined areas of responsibility. 'Public Order' and 'Police' are essentially the responsibilities of State Governments. However, the Central Government assists them by providing Central Paramilitary Forces (CPMFS) as and when required. Available at: www.wikipedia.com.

⁸ Police is an important enforcement agency. Its primary duties are the prevention of crime and maintenance of law and order. Bringing offender to justice and enforcement of law are the other important functions of the police.

⁹ Seventh Schedule of The Constitution of India, 1950.

¹⁰ Article 246 of the Constitution of India, 1950. For detail on this topic see generally: T.K. Tope, *Constitutional Law of India* (Eastern Book Company, Lucknow, 1982); V.D. Kulshreshtha, *Landmarks in Indian Legal and Constitutional History* (Eastern Book Company, Lucknow, 5th edn., 1984).

¹¹ I.P.C., 1860 is the main criminal code of India. It is a comprehensive code intended to cover all substantive aspects of criminal law. The Code does contain all the offences. This Code consolidates the whole of the law on the subject and is exhaustive on the matters in respect of which it declares the law; many more penal statutes governing various offences have been created in addition to the code. The I.P.C., 1860, sub-divided into twenty three chapters, comprises five hundred and eleven sections.

¹² Criminal Procedure Code, 1973 is the main legislation on procedure for administration of

The primary responsibility of the State is to maintain law and order so that citizens can enjoy peace and security. Life and personal liberty being very precious rights, their protection is guaranteed to the citizens as a fundamental right under Article 21¹⁴ of the Indian Constitution. This right is also internationally recognized as a Human Right. The State discharges the obligation to protect life, liberty and property¹⁵ of the citizens by taking suitable preventive and punitive measures which also serve the object of preventing private retribution so essential for maintenance of peace and law and order in the society. Substantive penal laws are enacted prescribing punishment for the invasion of these rights. When there is an invasion of these rights of the citizens it becomes the duty of the State to apprehend the person guilty of such invasion, subject him to fair trial and if found guilty to punish him. Substantive penal laws can be effective only when the procedural laws for enforcing them are efficient. This in essence is the function of the Criminal Justice System.¹⁶ The formal task of the criminal justice system is to process arrests, determine guilt or innocence, and in the case of guilt to specify an appropriate sanction. The major actors in the organization include the defendant, prosecutor, defence counsel, judge, police, court clerk, additional policemen, clerks, and social

substantive criminal law in India. The Code lays the rules for conduct of proceedings against any person who has committed an offence under any Criminal law, whether it is I.P.C or other Criminal law. The object of Criminal Procedure Code is to provide machinery for the punishment of offenders against the substantive Criminal law.

¹³I.E.A., 1872: The enactment and adoption of the I.E.A. was a path-breaking judicial measure introduced in India, which changed the entire system of concepts pertaining to admissibility of evidences in the Indian courts of law. Until then, the rules of evidences were based on the traditional legal systems of different social groups and communities of India and were different for different people depending on caste, religious faith and social position. The I.E.A. introduced a standard set of law applicable to all Indians. The I.E.A., identified as Act no. 1 of 1872, and called the I.E.A., 1872, has eleven chapters and 167 sections, and came into force 1 September 1872. At that time, India was a part of the British Empire. Over a period of more than 125 years since its enactment, the I.E.A. has basically retained its original form except certain amendments from time to time.

¹⁴ “No person shall be deprived of his life or personal liberty except according to procedure established by law.” For cases on this aspect see: *Maneka Gandhi v. Union of India*, AIR 1978, SC 597; *Kharak Singh v. State of U.P.* AIR 1963 SC 1295; *Hussainara Khatoon v. State of Bihar*, AIR 1979 SC 1360; *Bodhisatva Gautam v. Shubhra Chakraverti* (1996) 1 SCC490; *Charman Railway Board v. Chandrika Das*, AIR 2000 SC 998; *D.K. Basu v. State of West Bengal*, AIR 1977 SC 610.

¹⁵ Article 300 A: “A No person shall be deprived of his property save by authority of law.” Right to property, which one had the status of a fundamental right in our Constitution, is now relegated to a property leads to invasion of personal liberty. For cases on this aspect see: *Jeelu Bhai Naan Bhai Khachar v. State of Gujrat*, AIR 1995 SC 142; *State of Bihar v. Kameshwar Singh*, AIR 1951 SC 252; *K.T. Plantation Pvt. Ltd. v. State of Karnataka*, AIR 2011 SC 3430. For details see generally: M Rama Jois, *Legal and Constitutional History of India*(N.M. Tripathi Pvt. Ltd., Bombay, Vol. 1 , 1984); Dr. S.C. Tripathi, *Indian Legal and Constitutional History*(Central Law Publication, Allahabad, 2nd edn., 2009); V.N. Shukla, *Constitution of India*(Eastern Book Company, Lucknow, 9th edn., 1996).

¹⁶ Government of India Report : Committee on Reforms of Criminal Justice System (Ministry of Home Affairs, 2003), Available at: http://www.mha.nic.in/hindi/sites/upload_files/mhahindi/files/pdf/criminal_justice_system.pdf (Visited on July 12, 2010).

workers, the defendants' families and friends. Apart from these actors, the witness plays a vital role in the criminal justice system. A criminal justice system, whether it is adversarial¹⁷ or inquisitorial,¹⁸ entails the key elements of organization: institutionalized interaction of a large number of actors whose roles are highly defined, who are required to follow highly defined rules and who share a responsibility in a common goal that of processing arrests.¹⁹

To achieve the final goal of establishing a just society, various components of the criminal justice system, viz. the police, judiciary²⁰ prosecution and correctional services (in other words prison system),²¹ are expected to work harmoniously and cohesively. Success of one component may not

¹⁷ Adversarial system means a legal system used in the common law countries where two advocates represent their parties' positions before an impartial person or group of people, usually a jury or judge, who attempt to determine the truth of the case. The accused to be innocent and the burden of proof is in the prosecution to prove beyond reasonable doubt that he is guilty. The accused also enjoys the right to silence and cannot be compelled to reply.

¹⁸ Inquisitorial System means a legal system used in European Continent where power to investigate offences rests primarily with the judicial police officer. Burden of proof lies on accused and prove beyond reasonable doubt that he/she is not guilty.

¹⁹Malcolm M. Feeley, "Two Models of the Criminal Justice System: An organizational Perspective", 7(3) *Law & Society Review* pp.407-426 (1973). See also: Jenny Mcewan, "From Adversarialism to Managerialism: Criminal Justice in Transition Legal Studies", 31(4), pp. 519–546 (2011); Sam B. Warner and Henry B. Cabot, "Changes in the Administration of Criminal Justice during the Past Fifty Years",50(4) *HarvardLaw Review*pp. 583-615 (1937),Available at: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/1332682>,(Visited on 18 September 2012); John M. Darley, "Citizens' Sense of Justice and the Legal System, Current Directions in Psychological Science", 10(1), pp. 10-13, 2001, Available at: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/20182681>, (Visited on 17 September2012).

²⁰Judiciary means: The Indian Judiciary is partly a continuation of the British legal system established by the British in the mid-19th century based on a typical hybrid legal system known as the *Common Law System*, in which customs, precedents and legislative are all components of the law. The *Constitution of India* is the supreme legal document of the country. There are various levels of judiciary in India – different types of courts, each with varying powers depending on the tier and jurisdiction bestowed upon them. They form a strict hierarchy of importance, in line with the order of the courts in which they sit, with the *Supreme Court of India* at the top, followed by *High Courts* of respective states with district judges sitting in *District Courts* and Magistrates of Second Class and Civil Judge (Junior Division) at the bottom. Courts hear criminal and civil cases, including disputes between individuals and the government. The Indian judiciary is independent of the *executive* and *legislative* branches of government according to the Constitution.

²¹ The word 'Prison' and 'Goal' derive from the Latin words which mean respectively to "Seize" and "Cage". The Oxford English Dictionary defines prison as, "A place properly arranged and equipped for the reception of persons who by legal process are committed to it for safe custody while awaiting trial or punishment". According to the Government of India Prisons Act of 1870, 'Prison' meant any goal or penitentiary and includes the airing grounds or other grounds or buildings occupied for the use of the prison. Prison means any jail or place used permanently or temporarily under the general or special orders of a Local Government for the detention of prisoner. The *Encyclopaedia Britannica* defines, 'prison as an institution for the confinement of persons convicted of major crimes or felonies'. Prison traditionally defined as a place in which persons are kept in custody pending trial or in which they are confined as punishment after conviction. The word prison means different things to different people. To the law abiding it is a place where the criminals end up. To the criminal it may be a vague hazard or an unavoidable indignity. To the social inadequate it may be a shelter. To some isolated individuals it may be the only place where they can find some semblance of championship. To a prison officer it is his place of work. To the psychologist, a career in studying behaviour. But to

endure unless other components to achieve success of almost similar degree. For example, in a case, the police may succeed in arresting an accused and submitting a charge-sheet with sufficient evidence, however, if the prosecution is not able to present the case efficiently before the court, or if the court fails to assess the evidence in proper perspective, the accused will be set free and the efforts of the police will go in vain.²² Even if all these three components perform their parts well and the accused is convicted and sentenced to undergo imprisonment, it is not going to have a desired effect unless the sentence is executed properly. The jail authorities, instead of reforming the convict, may, unwittingly, aggravate the criminality in him by harassing him. They may also make the punishment ineffective by providing him such facilities and comforts to which he is not entitled. Thus, like in a relay race, all components of the criminal justice system have to play their role by supplementing the efforts of each other. Therefore, the criminal justice administration needs to be evaluated as a whole and not its components separately.²³

Like every civilized society in India has also adopted a criminal justice system. Socio-economic and political conditions prevailing during different phases of the history of India influenced its evolution. Accordingly, the objectives of the criminal justice and methods of its administration changed from time to time and from one period of history to another but it works on same principles and rules as other criminal justice system of the world work. Criminal justice system works for achieving the goal of pleasure of the people and welfare of the society. Of late, criminologist may argue that correction and rehabilitation of the crime-doers are also as important as the pleasure and welfare of the public. Theories of deterrence,²⁴ retribution²⁵ and incapacitation²⁶ etc. where in vogue

thousands of people, an experience which slows up time, which crows them together, sets them apart and changes the course of their lives.

²²Dr. Dalbir Bharti, *The Constitution and Criminal Justice Administration* 132(A.P.H. Publishing Corporation, New Delhi, 2002).

²³*Ibid.*

²⁴There are two basic types of deterrence—general and specific. General deterrence is designed to prevent crime in the general population. Thus, the state's punishment of offenders serves as an example for others in the general population who have not yet participated in criminal events. It is meant to make them aware of the horrors of official sanctions in order to put them off committing crimes. Examples include the application of the death penalty and the use of corporal punishment. Specific deterrence is designed—by the nature of the proscribed sanctions—to deter only the individual offender from committing that crime in the future. Proponents of specific deterrence also believe that punishing offenders severely will make them unwilling to reoffend in the future. A drunk driver, for example, would be deterred from drinking and driving because of the unpleasant experience he or she suffered from being arrested, or having his or her license taken away or his or her car impounded. The state must apply enough pain to offset the amount of pleasure derived from drinking.

²⁵This theory is based on the idea of vindictive justice, or a tooth for a tooth and an eye for an eye. The principle is that if a man has caused the loss of a man's eye, his eye one shall cause to be lost; if he has shattered a man's limb, one shall shatter his limb; if a man has made the tooth of a man that is his equal fall

until recently. But, such theories are found to have lost their grip in the modern concepts of criminal justice system. Criminologist may further argue that every society needs a minimum quantum of crimes for its existence, survival, dynamism and progress. This being so, deterrence, retribution or incapacitation etc. cannot and does not work effectively to curb down the extent of crimes in any society. History has proved that crimes co-existed with retribution and deterrence. Nevertheless, they too have some effect upon certain categories of people to desist from committing crimes, mostly petty in nature.

In early society (as there was no State or other authority) the victim had himself to punish the offender through retaliatory and revengeful methods.²⁷ This was, naturally, governed by chance and personal passion. Even in the advanced *Rig-Vedic* period²⁸ there is a mention that punishment of a thief rested with the very person wronged. Gradually, individual revenge gave way to group revenge as the man could not have grown and survived in complete isolation and for his very survival and existence it was necessary to live in groups. Group life necessitated consensus on ideals and the formulation of rules of behaviour to be followed by its members. These rules defined the appropriate behaviour and the action that was to be taken when members did not obey the rules. This code of conduct, which governed the affairs of the people, came to be known as *Dharma*²⁹ or

out, one shall make his tooth fall out. This is to pay back the wrong-doer for his wrong-doing. It means that the wrong-doer has to be made to suffer by way of retaliation, even if no benefit results thereby to him or to others. Historically, at first the instinct or the impulse of revenge was gratified by retaliatory measures on the part of the individual who suffered by the crime committed, or in the case of murder, by his relatives.

²⁶The term "incapacitation" when used in the context of sentencing philosophy refers to the effect of a sentence in terms of positively preventing the sentenced person from committing future offenses. This concept is different from the theory of specific deterrence in which an offender is punished to make him/her understand the specific consequences of his/her offense. Incapacitation aims to prevent future crimes by taking away the offender's ability to commit offenses. Pursuant to this theory, offenders are not rehabilitated. Criminals are put in jail not to teach them the consequence of their actions but to bring them under such an environment where they would not be able to engage in crime. Imprisonment incapacitates the prisoner by physically removing them from the society where they have committed the crime. Back-to-back life sentences, three-strikes sentencing, and other habitual offender laws are all examples of incapacitation.

²⁷ This method is very close to lynching which means Lynching differs from ordinary murder or assault because it is a killing that is committed outside the boundaries of due process by a mob that enacts revenge for an offense. During the late 19th century, lynching frequently enjoyed the approval of the public. It is a practice that was committed, ostensibly, in the name of justice. But the motivations for these killings were alien to the themes of justice and honour.

²⁸ The *Rig-Veda*, is about 2000 B.C.

²⁹The classical sanskrit noun *dharma* is a derivation from the root *dhr*, which has a meaning of "to hold, maintain, keep", and takes a meaning of "what is established or firm", and hence "law". It is derived from an older Vedic Sanskrit *n*-stem *dharman-*, with a literal meaning of "bearer, supporter", in a sense conceived as an aspect of *Rta*. The notion of *Dharma* as duty or propriety is found in India's ancient legal and religious texts. In Hindu philosophy, justice, social harmony, and happiness require that people live per *dharma*. The *Dharmashastra* is a record of these guidelines and rules. The available evidence suggests India once had a large collection of *dharma* related literature (*sutras, shastras*); four of the *sutras* survive and these are now

law. In course of progress man felt that it was more convenient to live in society rather than in small groups. Organizations based upon the principle of blood relationship yielded, to some extent, to larger associations the societies.³⁰

History comprises of the growth, evolution and development of the legal system in the country and sets forth the historical process whereby a legal system has come to be what it is over time.³¹ The legal system of a country at a given time is not the creation of one man or of one day but is the cumulative fruit of the endeavour, experience, thoughtful planning and patient labour of a large number of people through generations.

With the coming of the British to India, the Indian legal system changed from what it was in the *Mughal* period,³² where mainly the Islamic law was followed. The legal system currently in India bears a very close resemblance to what the British left with us. As per the needs of the changing times, changes and amendments were made, but the procedure which is followed now has its roots in the era of British-India. Little did the traders of the English East India Company while establishing their trade in India know that they would end up establishing their rule for about 200 years here. But the evolution of law as it is today did not come about in one go altogether. It was the Presidency Towns³³ individually that were first affected by this change in hands of the governance

referred to as *Dharmasutras*. Along with laws of *Manu* in *Dharmasutras*, exist parallel and different compendium of laws, such as the laws of *Narada* and other ancient scholars. These different and conflicting law books are neither exclusive, nor do they supersede other sources of Dharma in Hinduism. These *Dharmasutras* include instructions on education of the young, their rites of passage, customs, religious rites and rituals, marital rights and obligations, death and ancestral rites, laws and administration of justice, crimes, punishments, rules and types of evidence, duties of a king, as well as morality. According to *Kautilya*, the court of justice was to uphold the sacred law or dharma as dharma was eternal truth holding its sway over the world. Once more Kautilya underlines the importance of fair trial. He said that the king, who administered justice in accordance with sacred law (dharma), evidence (vyavahara), and ethics (nyaya), would be able to conquer the whole world bounded by the four quartets (caturantam mahim). For Dharama and Law see generally: Mahamahopadyaya Dr. Pandurang Vaman Kane, *History of Dharamasastra* (Sammamelan Mudranalay Prayag, Allahabad, 2nd edn. 1965). For details see also Subhamoy Das, "What Is Dharma", Available at: <http://hinduism.about.com/od/basics/a/dharma.htm> (Visited on 26 March 2010); K.L. Seshagiri Rao, "Practitioners of Hindu Law: Acent and Modern", Available at: <http://ir.lawnet.fordham.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=3431&context=flr> (Visited on 28 March 2010); Editorial, "Study on the Concept of Dharma", *The Hindu*. February 9 2010.

³⁰*Id.*, p.12.

³¹For details see, Available at: <http://www.lawyersclubindia.com/articles/Evolution-of-Law-A-short-History-of-Indian-Legal-theory> (Visited on 20 June 2010).

³² 1526-1858 A.D.

³³Presidencies in British India, also known as Provinces of India, included certain important areas of jurisdiction which were under direct control of the British East India Company from the beginning of the British rule and after 1857. The 3 major Presidencies in British India were The Bombay Presidency, Madras Presidency and Bengal Presidency. The Agra Presidency was one of the North western Provinces of British India. These Presidencies were administered directly under the crown of Queen Victoria (and following monarchs) who ascended the British throne. There were a number of different ways by which British India

of India after which the steps towards amalgamation of the judicial system were taken by the Charters of 1726 and 1753. To improve upon this, under the Regulating Act of 1773 Supreme Courts in the Presidency Towns and then under the Act of 1798 the Recorder's Courts at Madras and Bombay were established. These were ultimately replaced by the establishment of the High Courts under the Act of 1861, which are still running in the country.³⁴ It was only after independence in 1950 that the Supreme Court was established. Reforms and codifications were made in the pre and post independence eras and are still continuing.

There are two major systems in the world, on which criminal justice system works. They are the Adversarial and Inquisitorial System. One school of thought is that the Inquisitorial system followed in France, Germany, Italy and other continental countries. Adversarial system is followed in United Kingdom, United States of America, India and also some other countries. This takes us to the examination of the distinguishing features of the Inquisitorial system and Adversarial system.

AN APPRAISAL OF PRESENT CRIMINAL JUSTICE SYSTEM IN INDIA

Now-a-days criminal justice system in India is not functioning in as per expectation. Police, Prosecution, Judge, Court come often in the discussions of the common man in the street and in the press. They speak out many things about failures of our criminal justice system. Public meetings are organised just in front of the police stations to express the protest of the people to police doings and misdoings. *Dharnas* are conducted, mass petitions are sent and Writs are filed against the sub-system of criminal justice administration. The press is very vocal and it brings out the various ways miscarriage of justice is done and perpetuated in society. Custodial violence, lock-up deaths, suicides in police custody, illegal arrests by police and subsequent detention of the arrested, perfunctory method of investigation, undue influence in police functioning, witness threatening etc. come often and every time in the media and the people hold discussions about them.

Recently, the *Delhi gang-rape case* has opened a Pandora's Box and one of the most hotly debated topics emerging out of this is Police Reforms and improvement in the criminal justice system. In another example of *Ajmal Kashab case*, where the Indian judicial system took four years for the trial to be completed and Kasab's death sentence has been confirmed by the Supreme Court. This long drawn out trial was tom-tomed as showing to the world how the Indian system of justice is

was sought to be controlled. Beginning from East India Company ruling, when the country was basically looked as the eastern magical land of spices and brocades, and culminating in the strict regime of Queen Victoria, British India was administered by different modes. For details on Indian Legal History see generally books.

³⁴*Ibid.*

'fair'.³⁵ The emphasis was on 'showing the world' rather than earn any plaudits for India. This particular episode underlined the Indian slavish mentality and our constant effort to seek 'recognition' from the white man. This was no triumph of justice, but a shameful demonstration of our inferiority complex.³⁶ As expected, Kasab has put in his mercy petition to the President. If history is any guide, then Kasab's petition is also unlikely to be decided in the next 10, 15 years, if at all.³⁷

But increased violence, crime and terror attacks ought to generate a major debate on the state of criminal justice system in India. Even the members of the judicial system will concede that the system is near breaking point in India. An antiquated evidence law, judicial delays, abolishing the jury system have made justice more 'technical' than just. It is not just Bollywood movies that depict the rich and famous getting away with crime, reality imitates art.

The rich and famous in India have killed citizens in cases of drunken driving, been caught with AK-47 rifles, have killed endangered species, threaten the witnesses. While a person taking small bribes is often caught and punished, those looting several hundreds of crores seem to be forever on bail.³⁸ After some initial interest and pre-trial arrest, the case is forgotten by all. Not one of them has been sentenced and served time in jail.³⁹ Our convoluted morality shows more concern for the rights of the perpetrator than the victim. In defence of our non-functional system, we often invoke the Mahatma. The *Gandhian* dictum is if we follow the biblical eye for an eye and tooth for a tooth the whole world will go blind and become toothless. But the counter to this is that only if a law-abiding citizen follows this, only he will end up both blind and toothless.⁴⁰

No doubt, our criminal laws are not much advanced and updated to take present crime challenges. We have many provisions in the Acts and Code where the punishment or monetary upper limit and/or the prescribed fines are so abysmally low that they have lost all meaning.

As we all know, Police is principal agency for the enforcement of law and the policeman symbolize authority of the state. In fact the first line of defence against a criminal is the police. But the police has failed to come up to the expectations of the public for various reasons. The task of police has become more complex over the years. The traditional structure of police system is facing myriad problems prevalent in the present time. The equipment provided to police is quite outdated and

³⁵ Available at: <http://www.vijayvaani.com/ArticleDisplay.aspx?aid=2685> (Visited on December 2013).

³⁶ *Ibid.*

³⁷ Available at: <http://www.rediff.com/news/column/the-kasab-case-and-why-india-needs-judicial-reforms/20120925.htm> (Visited on October, 2012).

³⁸ *Jessica Lal Murder Case, B.M.W. Hit and Run Case, Priyadarsini Mattu Case, Aarushi Murder Case etc.*

³⁹ *Ibid.*

⁴⁰ *Ibid.*

transport and communication facilities are inadequate and their use and availability bound up in bureaucratic *red tapism*. The political interference also creates problem affecting the image of police. At times political interference is meant to camouflage inefficiency and dishonesty to secure the autocratic power in one form of another. Government over the years have manipulated the police for self gain.⁴¹

Investigation of criminal case is areas where the police are vested with a lot of discretion. Sometimes, these powers are abused by the police for practically genuine reasons, but quite often their reasons are imaginary and motivated. There wrong exercise of discretion results in damage to society in general and to the administration of criminal justice system in particular.

In the first place, there is inadequacy of the investigating staff. The police officers are hard pressed for time with multifarious commitments and, thus, not able to devote adequate time for investigational work⁴². A sample survey done at the instance of the National Police Commission in six States of the country revealed that on an average, the investigating officer is able to devote only 27% of his time on investigational work, while the rest of the time is taken by other duties connected with the maintenance of law and order, VIP bandobust, petition enquiries, court attendance, collection of intelligence and other administrative work.⁴³ The Committee on Internal Security constituted by the group of Ministers (GOI) in the wake of *Kargil* conflict in 2000 was informed by the DGP, Uttar Pradesh, of the startling fact that the police could devote only 13% of its time on investigations. Similarly, a random survey done at the instance of Second West Bengal Police Commission revealed that a Sub-Inspector of an urban police station in West Bengal, on an average, spent 20-25% of his time on investigational work; a Sub- Inspector in Calcutta City spent about 41% his time on it and a Sub Inspector in rural areas spent 16 to 18% of time in investigative work due to long distances involved. Inadequate number of I.Os. coupled with low percentage of their time being devoted to investigational work, resulting in perfunctory and delayed investigations, paved way for the acquittal of the accused.⁴⁴

An investigating officer on an average investigates 45 cases in a year. There is, however, a wide variation amongst States, with the workload of IO ranging from a low of 12.7 cases in Orissa to a high of 145.3 cases in Andhra Pradesh. The National Police Commission had suggested a workload

⁴¹ *Supra* note 104, p.54.

⁴² Fourth Report of the National Police Commission, *Available* at: <http://police.pondicherry.gov.in/Police%20Commission%20reports/4th%20Police%20Commission%20report.pdf> (Visited on 18 September 2011).

⁴³ *Ibid.*, p.3.

⁴⁴ *Ibid.*

of 60 cases per IO. Given the heavy commitment of police officers in law and order, VIP security and other 'Bandobast' duties, there is need for fixing a more realistic norm. It may be apt to add that the prevailing norms regarding workload of 10 in the CBI are two cases per year in the Central Units and 4 cases per year in the Territorial Units.

The Committee has interacted with police officers at the highest level as well as at the executive level. It has also discussed relevant issues with SHOs and their immediate supervisory officers and seen their work regarding investigation in some States. On the basis of observations and interaction, the Committee is of the opinion that for improving quality of investigation, the workload of an IO (or a team of IOs) should not exceed 10 cases per year. This norm is suggested for investigation of serious crimes. In the *Kashmiri Devi v. Delhi Administration and others*⁴⁵ the Supreme Court held:

...Prima facie the police has acted in partisan manner to shield the real culprits and the investigation of the case has not been done in a proper and objective manner. We are therefore of the opinion that in the interest of justice it is necessary to get a fresh investigation made through an independent authority so that truth may be known.

Technical or non-fulfilment of any procedural requirement or inadequacies of evidence or non-examination of material witnesses, mistakes in investigation and similar other factors have quite often contributed to acquittals. This amounts to failure of the courts' to search for truth to do justice. Therefore the Committee is of the view, that in such situations, the court concerned should not be allowed the shortcut of acquitting the accused.⁴⁶ A statutory obligation should be placed on the court to take such steps as may be necessary, or to issue such directions as may be required, to remove the deficiencies. This may include examining witnesses and directing fresh or proper investigation by any appropriate agency.

A notorious problem in the functioning of the courts, particularly in the trial courts is the granting of frequent adjournments, mostly on flimsy grounds. This malady has considerably eroded the confidence of the people in the judiciary. Adjournments contribute to delays in the disposal of cases. They also contribute to hardship, inconvenience and expense to the parties and the witnesses. The witness has no stake in the case and comes to assist the court to dispense justice. He sacrifices his time and convenience for this. If the case is adjourned he is required to go to the court repeatedly. He is bound to feel unhappy and frustrated. This also gives an opportunity to the opposite party to threaten or induce him not to speak the truth. The right to speedy trial is thwarted by repeated adjournments. Adjournment is a curse of the court.

⁴⁵AIR 1988 SC 1323.

⁴⁶*Supra* note 16, p.34.

Section 309 of the Cr.P.C., 1973 which regulates adjournments provides that adjournment should be granted only when the court finds it necessary or advisable for reasons to be recorded. It also gives discretion to the court to grant adjournment subject to payment of costs. However these conditions are not strictly followed and the bad practice continues.

The Malimath committee⁴⁷ suggested some points on the line of reform:- *Firstly*, the Criminal Justice system should be so constituted as to punish the guilty and protecting the innocent, the necessary implication being, the existing Criminal Justice System does not punish the guilty. The other implication could be punish the guilty first, and protect the innocent next;*Secondly*, quest for truth shall be the foundation of the Criminal Justice System, and everyone associated with the system shall actively pursue the quest for truth;*Thirdly*, how to find out the truth? The accused is a source of information of truth, and he cannot be allowed to remain silent. However, under Article 20(3)⁴⁸, he has a fundamental right to remain silent. So to get over this impediment, the recommendation is that the judge should “vigorously” and “pro-actively” question the accused for the purpose of discovering “truth”, and if the accused remains silent, draw adverse inference;*Fourthly*, the presumption of innocence and proof beyond reasonable doubt should be replaced by a standard of proof lower than that of “proof beyond reasonable doubt” and higher than the standard of “proof on preponderance of probabilities.” How to achieve this haphazard standard? The Report says, amend S. 3 of the I.E.A., to say that in a criminal case, a fact can be said to have been proved, if “the Court is convinced that it is true;” *Fifthly*, with a view to find out the truth and secure conviction, (and more conviction means a more efficient functioning of the Criminal Justice System) the evidence of ‘bad character’ and previous convictions should be allowed as a part of the prosecution case;*Sixthly*, the police should be allowed to extract confessional statement from the accused and for that purpose S. 25 of the I.E.A. be done away with and in its place such confessional statements be made admissible as in TADA Or POTA and lastly the Committee recommend, law like POTA or TADA should be part of our general law, in view of the increased terrorism in the country.

Instead of over-hauling the administration of the Criminal Justice System, which requires political will, the Government is still thinking in terms of Malimath Committee Report and its retrograde

⁴⁷*Supra* note 16, p.34.

⁴⁸The Constitution of India, 1950 says that ‘No person accused of any offence shall be compelled to be witness against himself.’ Cases on this aspect see generally: *M.P.Sharma v. Satish Chand* AIR 1954 SC 300, *Beera Ibrahim v. State of Maharashtra* AIR SC 1976SC 1167, *State of Bombay v. Kathukallu* AIR 1961 SC 1808, *Parshadi v. State of U.P.* AIR 1957 SC 211, *Nandani Satyapathi* AIR 1978 SC 1025, *Mohamad Dastgeer v. State of Madras* AIR 1960 SC 757, *Amrit Singh v. State of Punjab*, AIR 2007 SC 132, *Selvi v. State of Karnataka* AIR 2010 SC 1974.

recommendations. Justice should not only be done but seen to have been done. Public perception of any system of governance is shaped by a number of factors, the most important of which is the degree of security of life and property provided by the system.

Data Privacy :A Big Data Processing

Pranshul Pathak¹

Abstract

Big technology has been a significant commodity, offering streamlined activities and innovative growth prospects for many organizations. Big data, however, has expanded access to personal information and can potentially threaten user privacy and infringe data security regulations if stored. In the case of non-compliance that may also cause loss, system controllers and system processors are liable to enforce strict penalties. Within this article, we discuss the present state of regulatory legislation and analyze in the sense of big data processing different data security technologies and privacy conservation.²

This paper explores the present status of the laws in the light of big data processing, analyzing different data security and secrecy management strategies. Furthermore, as case studies concerned with confidential data and initiatives for compliance with privacy laws, we introduce and evaluate two real-life research ventures.³ They show which forms, according to the legal criteria, of information may become a danger to privacy, and the impact these methods have on the data processing method and test outcomes.

Keywords — large data; quantitative data; privacy; privacy; GDPR; anonymisation of data;

INTRODUCTION:

The phrase big data defines massive or complex data volumes that can be evaluated for information both organized and unstructured. A set of V-properties, such as the number, distance, and size, apply to broad data (i.e. NIST and Gartner). Big data have become resources today, where firms greatly improve their markets and client relations, and scientific work (in climate or biology science) has been extended and improved. Moreover, the tremendous volume, speed of generation and complexity of data require different storage and processing architectures (e.g. MapReduce or Apache Hive).

Although there is no question about the utility of big data processing, there is also high risk of privacy when it comes to personal data processing. This is primarily because of two dimensions of the study of big data. Second, the bigger the volume of data, the higher the probability of re-identification including with data sets that do not tend to have personal data connections.

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² NIST Big Data Public Working Group Definitions and Taxonomies Subgroup, “NIST Big Data Interoperability Framework: Volume 1, Definitions,” National Institute of Standards and Technology, Tech. Rep. NIST SP 1500-1r1, Jun. 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://nvlpubs.nist.gov/nistpubs/SpecialPublications/NIST.SP.1500-1.pdf>

³ V. Marx, “Biology: The big challenges of big data,” Jun. 2013. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nature.com/articles/498255a>

Furthermore, big data processing will derive fresh and more sensitive information from "harmless" personal data that has not been meant to reveal to the individual concerned.

Another popular case is the study of shopping habits in a department store for personalized (targeted) advertising, in which algorithms accurately concluded the pregnancy of a woman. These are places where risks to privacy, such as medical care or testing, can become much more important. A variety of technological approaches and legislation for secrecy data processing have been introduced and implemented to protect persons and their records. Nonetheless, it clearly takes more attempts to incorporate these methods in an information management system during the design phase; in many situations, these methods influence the system's performance.

For the past, however, businesses and other organisations have not been able to do so, but that has changed because of the impact of new rules and legislation on privacy.

In order to clarify how legitimate data security standards have been satisfied in research projects dealing with massive data and very sensitive personal information, this paper discusses problems related to data security during Big Data processing and focus on two cases studies (government sponsored projects^{2,3}). In addition, it addresses the implications of the privacy conserving strategies used on the collection of data and the tests.

Section II addresses the latest legal and technological issues relating to the handling of personal information. The document is structured as follows. Throughout Section III, two research projects with broad personal data sets are discussed and analyzed. Section IV addresses the effect of the data collection and effects of the programs on the privacy protection methods used. The article finishes in segment V.

BIG DATA ANALYSIS PRIVACY CONCERNS

LEGISLATIONS:

This article relies theoretically on the EU GDPR^[8], which came into effect in May 2018, and is the EU's General Data Protection Regulation. When data is collected by European people it is important for all the organisations within the European Union (EU), the European Economic Area (EEA) as well as for the organisations from other nations. GDPR thus has an influence on much of the world's largest businesses.⁴

The GDPR governs personal data collection, preservation and handling. Every identifying records that can be connected to a single human being is personal data. This not only contains overt personal identifying identifiers (e.g. full name, national identity number), but also indirect

⁴] K. Hill, "How Target figured out a teen girl was pregnant before her father did," Forbes, Inc, 2012.

identifying identification identifiers, such as contact numbers and IP addresses.⁵ Data not having such identifiers are usually considered private and outside the GDPR network. Big data analysis findings are most commonly mathematical reports that have no real interaction with people. The collection of confidential information is also a easy approach for all GDPR criteria.⁶

Yet anonymity is not a banal concept. However if parameters that can be identified explicitly are omitted from a data set, the combining of the data set with other information could re-identify persons. This de-anonymization strategy is referred to as a context information attack.

The Netflix competition in 2006 is a well-known case of re-identification. Netflix published a data package of 500,000 user reviews as part of a search to discover more precise approaches for film recommendation. The data collection deleted all personal data (PII) and released user IDs and movie ratings (Parts, Movie Data, Date) only (without any ties to the real identity) and the results. However, these statistics have been mixed with other information open to the public (for example IMDB ratings) and individual customers have been classified with high likelihoods.

The privacy of a data set can be calculated using various formal metrics (see the following section). GDPR deems the dataset private without an correct or clear concept of anonymity where re-identification is only feasible through extreme effort or by impossible means.

The GDPR describes a set of legislative, operational and technological standards for the collection of personal data and recommends various approaches. These are the most important concepts. Firstly, the collection of personal data in most situations is only allowed where the person involved has given his or her consent (Article 6). Exceptions occur where a statute or Policy calls for additional data analysis or accounts for "vital data topic needs." The restrictions apply. Therefore, the permission given must be limited to a particular data processing function (Article 5). The data controller (the data collection company) can not identify or modify the objective unilaterally at a later stage as an excessively general function.

Another theory for data processing is data reduction (Article 5), which involves the restriction of the compilation, storing and usage of personal information to data that is relevant, acceptable and essential to the operation of the reason for the processing of data. It should be remembered that pseudonymisation is explicitly defined as a method of data minimisation. For pseudonymised

⁵ M. Mostert, A. Bredenoord, M. Biesart, and J. J. Delden, "Big Data in medical research and EU data protection law: challenges to the consent or anonymise approach," *European Journal of Human Genetics*, vol. 24, no. 7, pp. 956–960, Jul. 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nature.com/articles/ejhg2015239>

⁶ A. Machanavajjhala, M. Venkitasubramaniam, D. Kifer, and J. Gehrke, "L-Diversity: Privacy Beyond k-Anonymity," in *22nd International Conference on Data Engineering (ICDE'06)(ICDE)*, 2006, p. 24. [Online]. Available: doi.ieeecomputersociety.org/10.1109/ICDE.2006.1

results, certain randomly generated identifiers are used to override identifying parameters. It normally has no negative influence on the data mining process and the data controller will ideally initiate it before the data is passed to the data processor.

The data controller can do this by connecting the data processing results to the recognizable parameters while they carry the pseudonym of mapping, which is often referred to as a pseudo-lookup Table. In addition to anonymized data, the data manager handling must be in compliance with the GDPR by using strategies for restful data security (such as encryption and improved access control).

Therefore, the GDPR needs 'a reasonable degree of protection adequate to the risk, technological as well as organizational steps' (Article 32) 6, usually requiring the implementation of methods such as data encryption, access verification, physics and (again) pseudonymization. The theory of storage restrictions, which limits data storage length to a fixed (necessary) time period, is an extension of this data minimization concept.

In the nature of the processing of data, we can also take note of the need for the "explicit" consent of the data subject to automated decisions with effect on the user (Article 22) and the processing of extremely sensitive data, for example biometric data (Article 9).

The GDPR will not discuss the words "big data" and "data processing." The definition above, though, shows that Big Data and the GDPR are not fully consistent. Big Data mining, for example, relies on processing vast volumes of data, also attuned to the data reduction theory. Therefore, new ideas are most commonly implemented in data analysis after data processing. Nevertheless, the people from whom the data were gathered initially gave consent for a specific reason.⁷

Therefore, data collection, if possible, from a legal point of view, of anonymised data should be carried out, otherwise the GDPR should be treated with great caution. A Data Privacy Impact Assessment (DPIA), for example; a privacy risk assessment to determine and evaluate how such acts or practices could have an risk on data security (Article 35).⁸ The damages which can be paid for non-compliance are dictated by the particular provisions of the law which have been violated by the company. The GDPR also gives people the right for redress for harm done by a violation of the Law to material and/or non-material.

⁷ C. Dwork, "Differential Privacy: A Survey of Results," in *Theory and Applications of Models of Computation*, ser. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, M. Agrawal, D. Du, Z. Duan, and A. Li, Eds. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2008, pp. 1–19

⁸ N. Li, T. Li, and S. Venkatasubramanian, "t-Closeness: Privacy Beyond k-Anonymity and l-Diversity," in *2007 IEEE 23rd International Conference on Data Engineering*, Apr. 2007, pp. 106–115.

In total, data processors and processors face regulatory penalties of up to 10 million euros (2 percent) of global annual sales (higher) for articles breakdowns: 8 (children's consent), 11 (identifiable processing), 25-39 (processors and managers' general obligations), 42 (certification) and 43 (bodi certification).

For infringes on Article 5 (data processing guidelines), 6 (legal basis for collection), 7 (conditions of consent), 9 (special types of data processing), 12-22, (data topic rights) and 44-49, up to EUR 20 million or four percent of the total global market value (the sum is higher).

TECHNICAL CONCERNS:

Professional protocols are required to fulfill the legal criteria set out in the previous section. Some methods for data mining privacy protection are given in this section. The works of Agrawal and Skrikant and Lindell and Pinkas are well known early approaches in this area.⁹

The first was the anonymization of data by manipulation and a special study was conducted on anonymous data for decision tree classification. The second one was separated into two distinct repositories (seems like a pseudonymization), which were both designed to evaluate the dataset using a special multipartisan measurement algorithm.

The standard components of the privacy analysis are seen here: anonymization (as successful as possible; pseudonymization at least) and potentially mining algorithms suited to this form of modified data.¹⁰

The attributes in a dataset are usually separated into four different groups to facilitate the anonymization process.

Explicit identity features, such as social security number or e-mail address, each directly linked to a single person.

- Quasi-identifiers: Attributes that do not link a person explicitly but will re-identify a individual when the meanings of many attributes are added together. Examples are: birth date, ZIP code or occupation.

⁹ N. Li, T. Li, and S. Venkatasubramanian, "t-Closeness: Privacy Beyond k-Anonymity and l-Diversity," in 2007 IEEE 23rd International Conference on Data Engineering, Apr. 2007, pp. 106–115.

¹⁰ L. Xu, C. Jiang, J. Wang, J. Yuan, and Y. Ren, "Information Security in Big Data: Privacy and Data Mining," IEEE Access, vol. 2, pp. 1149– 1176, 2014.

- Confidential material: features that include material that the data subject does not want or want to be connected to his or her person. Examples may include illnesses, financial conditions, sexual preference, current place.

- Non-sensitive information: characteristics not mentioned in any of the sections above.

This categorization is sadly not always clear: a rare disorder may even mark a human. There are large differences also in the categories: if you refer to a large city the place of residence can apply to millions of people but can also only point to a few individuals for small villages. A variety of anonymity models exist to measure the risk of anonymity and hence the danger of reidentification., l-diversity, t-closeness and differential privacy are the popular strategies.

This is a fact that confidential knowledge is most often very useful for data processing, but also for critics. If the object of an investigation is to relate specific identity to sensitive information, it is clear that anonymity cannot be obtained and the GDPR should be taken into consideration. Pseudonymization at least should be included in this situation. Nevertheless, data mining quite often seeks to connect quasi-identifiers with sensitive attributes to allow data to be anonymized. Popular methods of anonymization are :

- Delete: delete totally or substitution of an attribute value (typically asterisk "*"). • Deletion is required. Typically, this operation is performed with clear identifications.
- Generalization: replacement of attributes within the attribute taxonomy with more general or more abstract values, such as birth date / year of sex; age / year of age / year of death, ZIP code / first two digits ZIP code / first two digits. Typically this is achieved with quasi-identification devices.¹¹
- Permit: split data into categories and mold critical values into each category. It removes the relation between quasi-identifiers and sensitive data.
- Perturbation: substitution of values to eliminate the relation to the original results, while preserving equivalent statistic properties. The application of noise is a growing mechanism for disruption.¹²

The principles and approaches for anonymization are not only of scientific value but also used in implementation (e.g. Norwegian privacy authorities) standards. Obviously, the above-mentioned anonymization operations involve knowledge leakage and minimize the utility of the results. Using

¹¹ Norwegian Data Protection Authority, "The anonymisation of personal data," 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://www.datatilsynet.no/en/regulations-and-tools/guidelines/anonymisation/>

¹² V. Mavroeidis and A. Jøsang, "Data-driven threat hunting using sysmon," in In ICCSP 2018: 2018 the 2nd International Conference on Cryptography, Security and Privacy. ACM, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3199478.3199490>.

efficiency and anonymity metrics (see above), it is important to compare different solutions to anonymization and to consider a combination between privacy with benefits.

Anonymized databases can include data mining algorithms that are specially designed. The decision trees, a Bayesian hierarchy, support vector machines (SVMs), and stable Multiparty Computing are common examples of algorithms for which privacy preservation variants exist.

CONCLUSION:

This paper examined the impact of the data security regulations on Big-Data initiatives and explored how data protection strategies can be implemented through two case studies. The result was very unexpected. In one experiment, participants were asked to agree to address data confidentiality issues related to biometric data storage and distribution. Moreover, during the data processing process no issues were found. Data from an internal database have been used in the second phase.

In this sense, anonymization of certain areas of data was important and the data processing became more difficult and also constrained. It is also important to remember that a data security review will be undertaken at the earliest stages of the project for initiatives and technology concerned with sensitive data in order to recognize future threats to privacy and to adapt methods of research to take account of privacy protecting techniques.

Womb for Rent: Surrogacy and the Current Indian Scenairo

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The debate over surrogacy has emerged with the Lok Sabha clearing the Surrogacy (Regulation) Bill, 2019. The Bill aims to ban commercial surrogacy in India majorly with the intention of regulating the surrogacy practice in the country and to prohibit the potential exploitation of surrogate mothers. The Bill provides that, surrogacy shall be allowed only in the altruistic form and shall be available only to Indian nationals. It has been argued that homosexuals and single parents cannot take up surrogacy in India.

Surrogacy has evolved as an alternative path to achieve parenthood in the era of rising infertility. Not only for the married couples, surrogacy has proved to be a good solution for the singles and same sex couples to attain parenthood. The Judiciary has recognized the reproductive right of humans as a basic right. For instance, in *B. K. Parthasarthi v. Government of Andhra Pradesh*¹, the Andhra Pradesh High Court upheld ‘the right of reproductive autonomy’ of an individual as a facet of his ‘right to privacy’ and agreed with the decision of the US Supreme Court in *Jack T. Skinner v. State of Oklahoma*², which characterized the right to reproduce as “one of the basic civil rights of man”.

Surrogacy, as an *Assisted Reproductive Technology*, is not new and it has been in practice since ages. Surrogacy is a hope for childless couples who want to start a family but cannot bear a child themselves because of medical conditions. A surrogate mother is a woman who carries a child for someone else, usually an infertile couple. There are various types of surrogacy:

- *Natural/Traditional/Partial Surrogacy*: there is genetic relation of embryo with surrogate and it is done with her own ovum. Commissioning father can donate the sperm or the sperm can be taken from another male.³
- *Gestational/Full Surrogacy*: surrogate acts as a carrier of embryo which is genetically not related to her.⁴

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¹ AIR [2000] A. P. 156

² [1942] 316 US 535

³ A. Nigam, ‘Surrogacy: An Indian Perspective’ [2013] <<http://www.tcog.in/articles/1/1/surrogacy-an-indian-perspective.html> > accessed on 26 March 2020

⁴ Ibid

- *Commercial Surrogacy*: the surrogate enjoys payment for her renting her womb.
- *Altruistic Surrogacy*: no financial benefits are given to surrogate except medical expenses given as compensation by commissioning parents.⁵

India has gradually emerged as an International destination for commercial surrogacy.

In *Baby Manji Case* ⁶ the legal complications with regards to commercial surrogacy came to the forefront for the first time in 2008. The Supreme Court held that, commercial surrogacy is permitted in India with a direction to the Legislature to pass an appropriate law governing surrogacy in India. Thereafter, the successive draft Assisted Reproductive Technology Bills of 2008, 2010 and 2013 came up and were stated to be revised based on the recommendations of the Ministry of Law and Justice. In the year 2011, the Law Commission of India has submitted its 228th Report on '*Need for Legislation to Regulate Assisted Reproductive Technology Clinics as well as Rights and Obligations of Parties to a Surrogacy*' which insisted on a complete ban on commercial surrogacy in India.

The Surrogacy (Regulation) Bill, 2016 Bill lapsed with the dissolution of the 16th Lok Sabha. Thereafter, the Surrogacy (Regulation) Bill, 2019 was passed in Lok Sabha on August 5, 2019 to replace the 2016 Bill. The salient features of the Draft Bill are:

1. It seeks complete ban on commercial surrogacy and allows only altruistic surrogacy.
2. Surrogacy is permitted to only to intending couples who suffer from proven infertility; and not for producing children for sale, prostitution or other forms of exploitation.⁷
3. The Bill allows surrogacy to Indian Citizens only.
4. The intending couple should have a 'certificate of essentiality' and a 'certificate of eligibility' issued by the appropriate authority.
5. The certificate of eligibility will be issued to intending Indian couples who are married for at least five years and do not have any surviving child.⁸ The surrogate mother has to be a married close relative of the intending couple between 25 to 35 years of age.
6. The Bill prohibits transgenders, homosexual couples, live-in partners and single parents from having children through surrogacy.⁹

⁵ Ibid

⁶ *Baby Manji Yamada v. Union Of India & Anr.* [2008] 13 SCC 518

⁷ <https://www.prsindia.org/billtrack/surrogacy-regulation-bill-2019> , accessed on 27 March 2020.

⁸ Ibid

⁹ Ibid

7. The Bill proposes to regulate Hospitals and registered clinics that offer surrogacy in India. Any violations discovered will be subject to appropriate penalties with a jail term and fine. The surrogacy clinics shall have to maintain all records for a period of 25 years.¹⁰

While the introduction of the Surrogacy (Regulation) Bill, 2019, is a welcome step towards eliminating the existing regulatory vacuum in the commissioning of surrogacy in India, the provisions spelt out under the Bill stench of regulatory overreach and a faulty mechanism. The opponents of the Bill are of the view that the mandate of minimum five years of marriage is very unfair in today's times where marriages are generally late and prescribing the age limit is unreasonably restricting the commissioning parents of their right to have a family. Apart from this, the decision of the Cabinet does not seem to be in line with the constitutional mandate. Confining surrogacy only to the married Indian couples and excluding others on the grounds of nationality, marital status, sexual orientation or age, does not emerge to qualify the test of equality and has no connection with the intended objectives of the proposed legislation. Further, the right to life includes the right to reproductive autonomy — that includes the right to procreation and parenthood. It is not for the State to decide the modes of parenthood. Constitutionally, the State cannot interfere in the prerogative of a person(s) to have children, naturally or through surrogacy. The Rajya Sabha in its meeting on 21st November, 2019, referred the Surrogacy (Regulation) Bill, 2019 to a Select Committee comprising of 23 Members of Rajya Sabha to discuss various contentious issues related to the Bill. The Select Committee presented its report to the Rajya Sabha on 5th February, 2020. The Committee has recommended that a surrogate mother need not be a 'close relative' rather any 'willing woman' should be allowed to do it, the clause for five years waiting period for intending couples be removed, and single woman and people of Indian origin be allowed to access surrogacy among other such recommendations.¹¹

However, the report of the Rajya Sabha Select Committee is not binding on the Parliament. The Members of Parliament further examines the recommendations and move appropriate amendments and the Parliament then finalizes the Bill after voting on these amendments.

The Union Cabinet on 26th February, 2020 approved the Surrogacy (Regulation) Bill, 2020 after incorporating the recommendations of the Rajya Sabha Select Committee.¹² The 2020 Bill allows a '*willing woman*' and not just a '*close relative*' to become a surrogate mother and proposes that

¹⁰ Ibid, accessed on 28 March 2020.

¹¹ Ibid

¹² <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/cabinet-clears-surrogacy-regulation-bill/article30921456.ece>, accessed on 01 April 2020.

widows and divorced women can also benefit from its provisions, besides the infertile Indian couples. The definition of '*infertility*' has also been deleted in the new Surrogacy Bill of 2020. However, the new Surrogacy (Regulation) Bill, 2020 is still silent on the rights of LGBTQ community, single men to parenthood through surrogacy. The Surrogacy (Regulation) Bill, 2020 is a more ethical, moral and social legislation as compared to the restrictive Surrogacy (Regulation) Bill, 2019. It will be interesting to see whether this Bill becomes a law or it faces the same fate as the previous Bills.